

STUDIES IN SCURVY

BY

J. AXEL HÖJER

Former First Assistant at the Children's Clinic
of the Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm.
(Chief: Professor I. Jundell.)

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To

Professors Axel Holst and Theodor Frölich

This work is respectfully inscribed by

THE AUTHOR

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Preface.

The work which is here presented was begun in July, 1922. It would have been impracticable to fulfil it without the possibilities of technical aid offered by clinical laboratories. To Professors F. HENSCHEN and G. HÄGGQUIST, who have allowed me to avail myself of these possibilities and to whom I am also indebted for much helpful advice, I beg to express my gratitude. My thanks are also due to Professors I. JUNDELL and U. QUENSEL, to Assistant Professor Dr. C. KLING, Doctors R. NORDGREN, G. VESTBECK, H. DAVIDE, A. WASSÉN, S. SIVE, A. WALLGREN, Å. ÅKERLUND, the Dental Surgeon Dr. G. WESTIN, and others, for various reasons, some of which I have mentioned more particularly in my book. Special thanks are due to Doctor F. WAHLGREN and Fil. Doctor L. G. ROMELL who have kindly read the proofs.

My late father, the historian NILS J. HÖJER, who during all his life, beside his practical activity as a teacher, devoted himself to scientific work for science's sake, has been my model. My wife, SIGNE HÖJER, has been my helper.

I have allowed myself as a respectful token of admiration to inscribe my work to Professors AXEL HOLST and THEODOR FRÖLICH in Christiania, the first investigators in the field of experimental scurvy, whose work still remains unrivalled. Even though the exaggeration is evident in Funk's utterance (1922): »Since the experiments of Holst and Frölich, no real progress has been made (in experimental scurvy), in spite of the numerous publications that have appeared», yet his words show how high Holst and Frölich's works rank among all the rest.

Hagalund, Sweden. February 1924.

J. Axel Höjer.

PART II.

*Histo-pathological studies.***Preliminary notes.****Introductory.**

About the microscopic pathology of guinea-pig scurvy HESS writes in 1920: »Little has been added to the description so carefully depicted by HOLST and FRÖLICH 1907». About the microscopic pictures of scurvy in man he says, that »the study has been focussed so exclusively on the bones, that for many years, indeed until very recently, the other organs of the body were neglected». This judgment has lost but little of its validity during the latest years. Only in rare cases it is possible with absolute certainty to decide whether the changes seen in human scurvy are scorbutic or not, scurvy in man being so frequently associated with other disorders, deficiency diseases as well as infectious. It is only after experimental studies on animals that the pathology of human scurvy can be elucidated. HOLST and FRÖLICH's works are subject to the disadvantage — at that time quite natural — that in their basal diet A-vitamin and several other substances were lacking. When it comes to deciding whether microscopic changes are scorbutic, it is essential, however, that the basal diet should be complete except with regard to the antiscorbutic. This claim compels us to look at the results of most elder and many of the later investigators in the matter as being in some degree impaired by uncertainty.

For the studies in this second part of my work I have used the majority of the 96 guinea-pigs mentioned in Part I, as well as the majority of the 50 controls, which are mentioned in Part IV. For certain organs, I also use the tuberculous animals of the same series and besides 4 cases of infantile scurvy. The records of these three groups will be found in Part V.

Clinical symptoms. Macroscopic changes at the post-mortem.

I must set forth that I have found it impossible to draw a clinical curve according to HESS for the progress of scurvy. Especially the tenderness of the joints has been found too variable to form a basis for such a curve. My observations do not otherwise differ in the main from the current descriptions. With regard to the first noticeable symptoms, however, this has seemed to me most frequently to be a certain unwillingness to move, which can be observed before the changes of the joints seem to explain it and while the psychological condition still appears without fault. This weakness of muscle — for such it seems to be — is specially observed as a decreased motional effect on the guinea-pigs of a sudden and loud sound. Healthy guinea-pigs react with an instantaneous and swift movement. Guinea-pigs on scorbutic diet, that have not yet shown other symptoms, seem to perceive the sound as quickly and have an impulse to move, but the result is much less prompt than in the sound animals.

A macroscopic change that I have only found mentioned once in the literature — HART and LESSING speak of »eine Abknickung des Kopfes beider Tibien» in one of their monkeys — but which is very common in the final stage, is a deformation of the tibiae, consisting in a bending backwards of the tibia diaphyses towards the upper epiphyses. This gradually progressive curving has anteriorly a rounded outline, its axis being drawn frontally and horizontally and passing through the back of the tibia immediately below the upper epiphyseal line. It may become nearly a right angle. It renders walking extremely difficult and forces the animals to drag themselves along on their forelegs. This is the explanation of the pseudo-paralysis of the hinder half of the body which earlier investigators have mentioned and which I have also observed in these cases.

Another macroscopic change which I have not found noted in the literature, except by HOLST (»in many cases great proliferation of connective tissue across the costochondral

junction») but which is almost constant in advanced scurvy, is the appearance of certain strange connective-tissue formations on the pleural side of the intercostal musculature around the cartilage junction of the ribs, which show scorbutic changes. The shape of these formations vary. Sometimes they envelop the costochondral junction, on the upper or lower side, or both, like a rounded mould with a concave surface towards the rib and an outline merging imperceptibly into the musculature. Sometimes they appear as wedge-shaped irregular streaks, strongest at some distance from the costochondral junction. The colour is always pale grey, the surface glossy. The size varies, breadth and length measuring up to 10 mm., sometimes more, the thickness (diameter antero-posterior) 1—2 mm. These formations only occur in advanced cases, where there is a pronounced mobility in the anterior epiphyseal lines. They are seen chiefly in the 2nd—7th interstices. This localization strengthens the supposition that they are a reaction of the connective tissue to the abnormal movements in the epiphyseal line between cartilage and bone. Accordingly, we would see here, in connection with the appearance of new joints, a periarticular connective tissue developing. This interesting formation requires a special study from a purely mechanical point of view.

Technique.

At the *post-mortem* examination, which as a rule has been undertaken on the first day after death, sometimes later, the retained parts have been placed in a solution of formaldehyd of about 10 per cent. The solution gave a faint acid reaction. The continued treatment of the preparation has been the usual. The embedding has generally been done in paraffin. The bone preparations have generally been decalcified in 5 per cent. nitric acid, some only partially, others in Pommer's solution. Frozen sections for fat staining with Weigert Htx-Scharlachrot. For the rest the stain has been Ehrlich hematoxylin-eosin, if not otherwise stated. Further, the following special staining methods have been used.

For calcium: v. Kossa (3 % silver nitrate).

- » collagen: Hansen (iron trioxihematin 1 hour, after that Hansen's connective-tissue stain, according to Böhm-Oppel).
- » connective tissue: Weigert hematoxylin — v. Gieson.
- » fibrin: Weigert.
- » elastin: Weigert and Schulz (cresylic violet).
- » bone marrow, spleen: Giemsa.
- » iron: ferro potassium cyanid (Berlin blue reaction) and sulphurated ammonium — ferri potassium cyanid.
- » amyloid: metyl-violet.
- » chondroitin sulphuric acid: methylene-blue.

In the records of cases I have indicated for each case which parts have been examined. In all over 2.000 sections have been studied for Part I and II. For want of space the detailed description of each section is not quoted in the records, only the results for different organs are summarized in the different chapters.

Nomenclature.

As denomination for the substance, the absence of which causes scurvy, I use alternately »vitamin C» and »the anti-scorbutic», in conformity to most investigators. My preferring the latter, as a rule, is due to the fact that this name expresses a fundamental biological quality, the basis for the specific identity reaction of this substance. We may possibly, for want of greater chemical knowledge, as with the ferments, have to keep for a long time still to this biological nomenclature (ARON). If I have a certain sympathy for this opinion of Aron's, I must on the other hand vividly oppose his proposal to call vitamin B »ansatzfördernder» and vitamin A »resistenzerhöhender Nährstoff-Faktor». Irrespective of other nutrition factors (*e. g.* calcium), it must be emphasized that the antiscorbutic is both ansatzfördernd and resistenzerhöhend. This mistake of Aron's shows better than anything how prudent those investigators have been who provisionally have fixed

a neutral nomenclature. As name of a group the word vitamin has become most widely adopted and ought to be kept till another can be found with a better chemical foundation. As to the other members of the vitamin group, for the present I use the expression vitamin A for the vitamins contained in cod-liver oil, till the question about their division into different, biologically definable substances (McCOLLUM etc.) is further analysed. The same thing applies to vitamin B as representing the group of vitamins in yeast or bran.

Classification of scurvy in different stages.

Up to the present time scurvy has been clinically divided into a latent and a manifest stage. The first sure clinical sign constitutes the difference, which often, however, is very difficult to fix. An intermediate stage, during which suspected symptoms occur, is common and can have rather a long duration. It has been called differently: subacute scurvy (HESS); formes frustes (LESAGE); abortive forms (KOCH); préscorbut (GODLEVSKI).

From a patho-anatomical point of view, there is only one attempt at classification, that of DELF and TOZER, who distinguish between five stages: »incipient, definite, acute, chronic definite, and acute chronic scurvy». This classification is deficient in many respects. The choice of the names is not a very happy one as they do not cover the meaning. The differentiating principle is not clear. Perhaps the intention of the authors was rather to single out certain types of the rib changes, than to propose a classification of scurvy in different stages.

Such a classification, however, is necessary for the discussion of the scurvy problems. As the conditions of the experimental animals, especially the patho-anatomical changes, are used for illustrating and elucidating the conditions in man, it is desirable that a common classification of the stages should be adopted, where the clinical and the physiological points of view can both have their due. An important task for the

near future is to make clear the finer physiological and patho-anatomical changes in the different stages of experimental scurvy. Only then order will be brought into the clinical findings.

In accordance with the denominations of certain earlier authors, I propose the following scheme for classification of scurvy in different stages.

Scorbut manifestus	{	Sc. manifestus gravior	
	{	Sc. manifestus mitior	
Scorbut latens	{	Sc. latens gravior	
	{	Sc. latens mitior	{ Sc. latens extensus
			{ Sc. latens levior

As differentiating principle, the clinical difference is here taken in the first place. Is there any clinical sign of scurvy, alteration of the complexion, standstill of weight, hemorrhage, typical Roentgen picture? The disease then is manifest. If clinical signs are absent, it is latent.

The second differentiating principle is physiological. Has the patient altogether been without antiscorbutic in his diet? The scurvy then is absolute or *gravior*, whether it has yet led to manifest symptoms or not. If, on the other hand, there has been a certain dose of antiscorbutic in the diet, it is a case of *scorbut mitior*, whether this has become manifest, not yet had time to develop, or possibly seems to remain latent. At the *post-mortem* examination of such a latent case, typical changes can be met with in different parts of the bone system, especially in the long bones: *scorbut mitior extensus*. Or else patognomonic symptoms are seen only in the teeth: *scorbut mitior levior*.

The physiological differentiating principle may also be made the chief principle, when the scheme will have the following arrangement:

Scorbut absolutus or gravior	{	Sc. gravior manifestus	
	{	Sc. gravior latens	
Scorbut mitior	{	Sc. mitior manifestus	
	{	Sc. mitior latens	{ Sc. latens extensus
			{ Sc. latens levior

In all cases we get the same five forms of scurvy, which shortly may be characterized thus:

1. *Scorbut gravior manifestus*.

The food has been totally lacking in antiscorbutic. This form has been the one most usually induced in the experiments undertaken so far. The changes are of a very deep-going nature and soon destructive to life. Quantitatively the patho-anatomical changes have a smaller extent on account of the rapid development of the disease.

2. *Scorbut gravior latens*.

The same thing applies to this form, which only differs from the preceding in that no clinical sign has yet become evident. This form may be divided into *scorbut gravior latens extensus*, *levior* and *initialis*, as is *scorbut mitior latens*. However, this division has not the same importance, at least not in the present work.

3. *Scorbut mitior manifestus*.

Here a certain dose of antiscorbutic has been included in the food, up to a half of the protective dose. With this lengthening of the life-time the scorbutic changes have had time to develop and show quantitatively a larger extent than in the forms indicated as *gravior*. Most cases of manifest human scurvy may be said to belong to this category.

4. *Scorbut mitior latens extensus*.

When guinea-pigs have a half to two thirds of the minimum protective dose, the scurvy generally remains latent some considerable time (for months). At the *post-mortem* examination, typical scorbutic changes are found in the long tubular bones and several other organs.

5. *Scorbut mitior latens levior*.

When guinea-pigs have had nearly the protective dose (0.8—0.9 of the minimum protective dose), there are no changes to be seen in the bone system generally; they are only found

in the teeth. The other organs show no obvious, in any case no pathognomonic changes.

About the merely functional scurvy, *scorbut initialis*¹, that is seen in the first week of scorbut gravior and may also be presumed to be a form of scorbut mitior latens, see p. 126.

In the research about human scurvy the latent forms will probably come to play a very great rôle in the near future. It is therefore of special importance to emphasize the difference between a latent case, which is only the first stage of a manifest grave illness and which is in itself severe, and the milder latent forms where the findings are different. It may *a priori* be taken for granted that scorbut mitior latens levior and initialis nowadays are the forms most common in man.

As besides the antiscorbutic dose administered also the time for which the animal has lived after the beginning of the experiment is of significance for the appearance of the changes, the reports ought to include information about the life-time, counted in days, during the experiment. For instance thus: No. 141, scorbut mitior manifestus, 0.3 min. pr. d., 52 days.

Against this proposed classification of scurvy, several objections might be raised. First of all may be said that clinically a case may one day get no antiscorbutic in the diet, and the next day a completely protective dose; and experimentally Howe has acted in this way. But such cases will hardly fit into any system. Further, the dividing of scorbut mitior latens into two groups on a patho-anatomical principle may be criticized. Any other point of view, however, is impossible to take at present, and with regard to the great importance of the latent cases I have thought this division would become useful.

Grouping of my animals within the different stages of scurvy.

In order to avoid repetition, I include here the animals infected with tuberculosis, the figures for which are printed

¹ I thus use this name for a different stage than do Delf and Tozer.

in italics. Those animals in whom an acute infection has been stated are marked with an asterisk. The average life time means the number of days from the beginning of the experiment till the animals' death.

1. *Scorbut gravior manifestus.*

No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5*, 6, 7, 8, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27*, 28, 31*, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46*, 47, 48*?, 49*, 50*, 51, 52*?, 53, 54*, 55*, 56, 57*, 71, 72, 73, 74, 91, 92, 93, 112, 113, 115, 116*, 117*, 118, 119.

In all 57, of which 13 (22.8 %) with an acute infection.
Average lifetime 28.4.

2. *Scorbut gravior latens.*

No. 29*, 30*, 38*, 94*, 114*?.

In all 5, all (100 %) with acute infection.
Average lifetime 6.2.

3. *Scorbut mitior manifestus.*

No. 58, 59, 60*, 61, 65, 66*, 67, 68, 69, 70, 75, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87*, 88, 89, 90*, 121*, 122, 123*, 124, 125*, 126, 127*, 131*, 132, 133.

In all 29, of which 9 (31.0 %) with acute infection.
Average lifetime 45.2.

4. *Scorbut (mitior) latens extensus.*

No. 18, 63*, 120*, 128*, 129*, 130*, 135*, 136*, 137*, 138*, 139, 140, 141, 142*, 143*, 148, 149.

In all 17, of which 11 (64.7 %) with acute infection.
Average lifetime 49.4.

5. *Scorbut (mitior) latens levior and initialis.*

No. 16, 62*?, 64*, 79*, 80*, 134*, 144, 145*, 146, 147, 150, 151, 152*, 153*, 155, 156, 157*, 158*, 159*, 160, 161, 162, 163*, 164*, 165, 166*.

In all 26, of which 14 (53.8 %) with acute infection.
Average lifetime 50.0.

6. *No scurvy.*

a) With complete dietary, No. 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 19, 95, 96, 97*, 98, 99, 100, 101, 102, 103, 104, 105, 106, 107*, 108, 109, 110, 111, 167*, 168, 169, 170, 171, 172*, 173, 174, 175*, 176*, 177*, 178, 179*, 180*, 181, 182, 183, 188, 189.

In all 45, of which 9 (20 %) with acute infection.
Average lifetime 82.9.

b) With relative inanition, No. 184, 185, 186, 187*.

In all 4, of which 1 (25 %) with acute infection.

c) With dietary deficient in A-vitamin, No. 81, 82.

In all 2, without acute infection.

7. *Healing scurvy.*

No. 76, 77, 78.

In all 3.

CHAPTER I.

The bone formation in scurvy. (Figs. 1—51.)

The opinion asserted in recent years, that the bone formed in the course of scurvy, before the total arresting of bone formation, is normal bone, proves to be incorrect. It is shown that in scurvy a bone is formed, the appearance of which differs more and more from the normal, till all bone formation stops. This less differentiated bone is described in teeth, in endosomal and enchondral bone formation. Quotations from the literature show that earlier investigators have observed and described these formations, though, as a rule, they have misinterpreted them.

Teeth.

A closer analysis of the changes in the teeth in scurvy. The statements of earlier writers are completed, rectified or confirmed.

Historical notes.

»That macroscopic changes take place in the teeth by guinea-pig scurvy has been noted by many investigators. The teeth become somewhat yellow, lose their glistening appearance and occasionally break off. The molars commonly become loosened, so that they can readily be removed from their alveolar sockets; less frequently, this is true of the incisors.» (HESS.) In 1916, JACKSON and MOORE held they had found, »that with marked changes in the teeth there was often great dilatation of the veins in the pulp attended by more or less hemorrhage, and that in guinea-pigs, fed on oats and hay, there was almost complete necrosis in the pulp of the molars». ZILVA and WELLS (1919) were the first to give details about the microscopic changes. They studied teeth of guinea-pigs and monkeys. Unfortunately, the illustrations in their work are such as to make it necessary for us to confine ourselves exclusively to the text. According to this, a fibroid degeneration of the pulp sets in. This kind of degeneration which up till now has been attributed only to inflammatory causes, would thus here for the first time be shown to be due to a dietetic cause. In the pulp of the scorbutic teeth there is, according to these writers, »no trace of interstitial cement substances. Nerves, cells; blood vessels, odontoblasts, are no longer recognizable, right up to the apex of the root. The change appears to start first in the odontoblastic cells at the top of the pulp, working down towards the apex followed by distended blood vessels and hemorrhage. Then complete fibroid degeneration follows». They also state, that »the tooth is one of the first, if not the first part of the system to be affected by the deficiency of antiscorbutic material in the diet». In 1921, E. F. ROBB, GRACE MEDES, McCLENDON, GRAHAM and MURPHY published a study of scurvy and its bearing on the preservation of the teeth. They have »sectioned teeth of quite a number of guinea-pigs and always found marked changes, if antiscorbutic was not included in the diet. The changes in the teeth proper were surprising. There was marked hy-

peremia of the pulp, with some hemorrhage. The odontoblasts lost their tall columnar form and secreted osteodentin very rapidly. The osteodentin nearly filled up the cavity in some cases». P. HOWE has during the last years after experiments on a large scale, intended to make clear the effect of diet upon the teeth, published a number of incomplete and rather fantastic communications and figures. He induced scurvy in guinea-pigs and monkeys by giving them a diet, free from antiscorbutic, and only now and then, when manifest symptoms of scurvy had developed, giving them a dose of orange juice, which he does not indicate exactly, only it was large enough to prevent the animals from dying. As a consequence of this, Howe finds pyorrhea alveolaris developing, and also a process which he considers homologous with caries dentium in man. Part of the teeth of Howe's guinea-pigs have been examined histologically by TOVERUD, who describes them as follows: »The normal orthodentin is largely substituted by osteodentin, which, incorporating degenerated odontoblasts, reaches far down towards the apex of the tooth. There is only a very narrow space of orthodentin surrounding it. *The pulp tissue is so degenerated that one can scarcely recognize any of its normal elements. In the more severe cases there is nothing at all left of the proper pulp tissue, only some degenerated odontoblasts¹*, which may be seen scattered around. In many cases there seems to have been a fatty degeneration.»

In chemically examining the scorbutic teeth Toverud found a decreased calcium proportion and an increased proportion of magnesium.

That is all I have found in the literature upon the subject. The criticism will be given in discussing my own results.

Own investigations.

I have examined the lower jaw of 150 of my guinea-pigs. The section has been made frontally, at right angles to the

¹ The italics are mine.

longitudinal axis of the lower jaw through the middle of the foremost molar on each side. (Figure 1.) Hereby four teeth have been reached in each section. There has been a longitudinal section of the molars and a cross section of the incisor roots running inside and below these, one on each side. The topography of such a section is shown in Figure 2. For the interpretation of the sections I have collaborated with a dental surgeon, Dr. GÖSTA WESTIN. He is at present occupied in an intensive study of all my guinea-pig jaws in series of sections and will report on them as well as on continued experiments with own material. The result of my investigation, therefore, is given here only in broad outline. Embedding in paraffin has been found not very suitable for the study of summary pictures, as the molars and the jaw-bone are easily frayed. On the other hand it is more advantageous than celloidin sections for the study of the cells and the finer structure.

A normal picture from guinea-pig teeth is shown in Fig. 3, Case 188, as well as in Cases 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 19, 95, 96, 189.

An incipient scurvy is noticeable in the tooth already 8 days after the starting of absolute scurvy diet. The first change affects the odontoblast layer. This layer which forms the intermediate link between pulp and dentin, has normally a very regular structure of long, slender, parallel cells with processes into the dentinal tubules. In scurvy this regularity is broken, and at the same time a hyperemia appears in the pulp. The parallelism of the odontoblasts becomes less pronounced. At intervals more rounded, osteoblast-resembling cells are seen in their stead. In these places the corresponding part of the predentin seems to have lost the protoplasmic processes from the odontoblasts. It lacks Tomes' canals and seems amorously calcified. (Fig. 4, 5, 7, Cases 29 and 38.) In the dentin, however, which was already calcified at the onset of the scurvy, Tomes' canals seem to remain, and here they are widened (Fig. 5). Inside the calcified dentin, which re-

sembles an amorphous cement, a hard tissue is deposited in the course of the process, stained blue-grey by hematoxylin (Fig. 6, Cases 29, 79, 80). In the place of the odontoblasts, at the inner, notched edge of this tissue, osteoblast-resembling cells are seen. Similar cells are also seen further in towards the centre of the pulp (Case 63) and in different places the above-mentioned hard tissue reaches into the pulp in diversified strands, surrounded by osteoblast-resembling cells (Fig. 7 b, Cases 4, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 35, 48, 49, 50, 54, 57, 59, 60, 66, 67, 83, 86, 87). These strands or columns already from the first show a certain regularity in their arrangement, standing radially in relation to the centre of the pulp. They are early connected by transverse columns and show a distinct bone structure (Fig. 8, 9). In sections prepared by grinding (Sonnenburg) we have verified that this is calcified bone. In Fig. 9 and 10 it is also seen that the pulp has become rich in osteoblast-resembling cells, which between them have islets of homogeneous, eosinophile tissue. This tissue is supplanted in the next stage by calcified bone, which thus may occupy most of the former space of the pulp (Fig. 10, Case 58, 88). Thus part of the pulp tissue, osteoblasts, other pulpa cells and vessels are enclosed within canals, which partially are very narrow, containing in a cross section one single cell, resembling a bone corpuscle, or a capillary, while others are wider, resembling Haversian canals (Fig. 11 and 12). Thus, the character of this pulpa bone is spongy and porous. In longitudinal sections of molars (Fig. 13) it is seen how this new bone formation is already strongly developed in the parts of the pulp which are next to the crown, whereas it is still weak at the open root apex.

In the development described above, dilated veins show in the pulp (Fig. 6, 8, 9), and more or less rounded or oval spaces (Fig. 9, 10), which give the impression of a *hydrops ex vacuo*. In some places there are hemorrhages, generally few and small.

The extent of this new growth of pulpa bone seems to depend on the course of the scurvy. In cases where the pro-

gress is rapid, there being no antiscorbutic substance in the diet, the bone formation is often reduced to a thin layer next to the calcified predentin with only small columns, or none, growing into the pulp (Fig. 14, 15, 17, Cases 1, 23, 50). If, however, there has been a small amount of antiscorbutic in the food, which has somewhat lengthened life, but not precluded the fatal issue, the bone formation is more vigorous. In the former group of cases we sometimes find the picture of a lively resorption of pulpa bone. In the pulp large hydroptic spaces appear (Fig. 15, 17) and the thin lamella of newly formed pulpa bone lying close to the dentin is perforated by numerous lacunæ, filled with cell-syncytia, »osteoclasts» (Fig. 16). There is no trace of any odontoblasts, and the remaining osteoblasts resemble spool-shaped cells of connective tissue.

If the animals, however, after a time of scorbutic diet, receive a life-preserving daily dose of antiscorbutic substance, the development becomes a different one. Series 17, animals 75—78, is an instance of this. See weight charts, Fig. 111. In Case 75, that died of mitigated scurvy, we find the bone formation very vigorous right in towards the centre of the pulp (Fig. 18). When the three other animals in the series had had orange juice added to their diet, recovered and had been killed, we see the pulpa bone reorganized to irregular dentin (Fig. 19, 20, 21). Slender odontoblast-like cells appear again, even if they are not at once as regularly arranged as in animals which are sound from birth. The bone columns are perforated by Tomes' canals, running irregularly. This irregular dentin possesses at the same time bone canals with cells and bloodvessels, and dentin canals, and it may therefore rightly be called osteodentin.

The stage of development of the pulpa bone may be somewhat different in animals fed on the same dietary, and corresponds to the differences in the progress of the scurvy. As examples may be quoted the animals 1 and 3 in Series 1. The former died first of the eight animals in the series. The pulpa bone does not seem to have been developed in any high degree. In any case the resorption has soon predominated,

and at death only inconsiderable rests are to be seen. Animal No. 3, which died last in the series, 13 days after the first, shows the pulp to a large extent filled by pulpa bone. If the changes thus may differ in degree in different animals fed on the same dietary, they seem in nature closely to correspond within each group.

This interpretation of the connection between the different pictures presented by the sections from my 97 first animals, is confirmed through the study of the teeth in those animals which have received a carefully titrated dose of anti-scorbutic, consisting of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.8, and > 1.0 of minimum protective dose (m. pr. d.). The changes are seen in Figs. 22—30 and may be shortly summarized as follows.

0.1 m. pr. d. Fig. 22. Highly widened Tomes' canals in the old dentin. The new formation, reaching towards the centre of the pulp, consists of bone.

0.2 m. pr. d. Fig. 23. Highly widened Tomes' canals in the old dentin. The new formation, reaching towards the centre of the pulp, consists of bone, in the outer (oldest) part of which there is seen a trace of Tomes' canals.

0.3 m. pr. d. Fig. 24. The same picture, but with a less distinct widening of the dentinal canals in the old dentin and less pronounced formation of bone in the pulp.

0.5 m. pr. d. Fig. 25. Widening of Tomes' canals not very distinct in the old dentin. The new formation consists of dentin and bone. The dentin closes round the old dentin, is lighter in colour than this, has an irregular inner edge and an irregular odontoblast layer. The bone is seen in two symmetrical places to reach in towards the pulpa centre.

0.7 m. pr. d. Fig. 26 and 27. Similar picture.

0.8 m. pr. d. Fig. 28 and 29. No distinct change of the old dentin. The new formation consists entirely of dentin, of a lighter colour, with irregular inner edge and disturbed odontoblast layer. Hyperemia in the pulp.

>1.0 m. pr. d. Fig. 30. Normal tooth picture. Well arranged odontoblast layer, predentin and dentin of normal appearance. Possibly some hyperemia in the pulp.

Fig. 26, compared to Fig. 27, and Fig. 28, compared to Fig. 29, show that it is not so much the time during which a guinea-pig has had scurvy, as the antiscorbutic dose it has received, that is determinative of the tooth picture. In the first couple the animals have received 0.7 of the minimum protective dose during 22 and 92 days respectively. The tooth picture is principally almost identical. In the latter couple an antiscorbutic dose of 0.8 has been given during 29 and 92 days respectively. The tooth pictures are principally identical and well defined from that of the first couple. This amazingly sharp difference between groups, where the difference of antiscorbutic dose is only 0.1 of the minimum protective dose, is in most cases invariably found.

Such is the picture of the changes in the teeth in scurvy, which the study of the sections have given to me and Westin. It gives no reason for altogether accepting the descriptions and explanations offered by earlier writers. But on the other hand we have been able to verify certain details of their investigations. Like ZILVA and WELLS, and TOVERUD, we have found that the changes are very early, that they begin in the crown part of the pulp and spread towards the root. These changes, however, by no means consist of »a total fibroid degeneration». A few cells may degenerate and die, the odontoblast layer as a regular, creeper-like covering of the inner even surface of the dental bone may disappear and necroses occur in the pulp. In the place of the odontoblast layer we see in any case cells appear with continued activity, real osteoblasts, and an active new formation of bone instead of dentin sets in. In no case we have been able to find a picture where the term fibroid degeneration with reason can be applied to the scorbutic changes in the teeth, nor have we found any case, where such changes affect the whole of the pulp, so that »no trace of cellular organization can be found anywhere». It is remarkable that Zilva and Wells among their illustrations, moreover rather indistinct, do not show any one that can be interpreted in that manner. The one among our sec-

tions, which most resembles one of their pictures, is an oblique section of a longitudinally cut molar, in which the pulp centre has not been reached (Fig. 31). But even here, it is not necrosis but newly formed bone.

ROBB etc. have approached the right explanation nearer than ZILVA and WELLS. They interpret, as has already been mentioned, the »fibroid degeneration» of those two writers as a formation of osteodentin, secreted by the odontoblasts. By the term osteodentin, however, we evidently ought to understand a tissue which mainly possesses the qualities both of bone and dentin. The hard tissue formed in the pulp of the teeth in fully developed scurvy resembles bone, but it lacks the constitutive quality of dentin, Tomes' canals. Nor can the formation of pulpa bone be ascribed to odontoblasts, as the bone-forming cells are not like those but look like osteoblasts. There is certainly a great probability that the regular odontoblast layer is changed into irregular strings of osteoblasts. But Robb etc. give no details of these changes described by us. On the other hand, the name of osteodentin may with reason be applied to the irregular dentin, which is formed when the scorbutic pulpa bone, after the recovery of the animal, is reorganized by the reappearing odontoblasts (an observation, not described by Robb and his colleagues), and to the dentin, formed in scorbut mitior latens.

HOWE does not seem himself to have undertaken any histo-pathological examinations, and those of TOVERUD, mentioned above, are very summary and, as is shown, in part incorrect.

We recapitulate and summarize the changes in the teeth produced by scurvy, as we have interpreted the pictures, in the following manner.

1. *The gradual change of the odontoblast layer.* This seems to be a sure sign of scurvy and one of the earliest changes to set in. The odontoblasts assume another shape, grow shorter, more rounded, and show another arrangement, the normal regular, creeper-like formation makes way to a layer, which in some places curves in towards the centre of the pulp

and is soon split through the cells secreting a hard tissue between themselves, so that the syncytial character of the cell layer does not plainly appear. The odontoblasts have been transformed into osteoblasts placed in bone canals. Incidentally may be pointed out how well this process agrees with the conception of the syncytial character of bone which Professor G. HÄGGQUIST has lately expressed in the Society of Swedish Physicians.

2. *The amorphous calcification of the pre-dentin.*

3. *Widening of Tomes' canals in the dentin formed before the onset of scurvy.*

4. *New formation of bone instead of dentin.* This bone is first lying as a thin layer inside the calcified pre-dentin, but soon extends reticularly towards the centre of the pulp. This bone has a spongy, porous character.

5. *Dilatation of vessels and in early stages hyperemia; sometimes hemorrhages in the pulp.*

6. *Atrophy and resorption of pulpa tissue,* pulpa cells, the newly formed bone and the old dentin. This resorption, which, as everywhere in bone formation, will surely be found also with scurvy in all stages, appears more distinctly after all the new bone formation in the final stage has stopped, and may proceed so far, that in the place of the pulpa tissue there is seen nothing but some large hollows filled with fluid.

7. *In the healing of the scurvy* — at an earlier stage — *reorganization of the pulpa bone into irregular dentin, osteodentin,* with bone canals and dentinal canals.

8. *In a scurvy which is latent all through or very much mitigated,* when at least half the amount of antiscorbutic needful to an individual is provided — forms which are the most common in man — *the progress is similar, though not so pronounced and presents pictures, that differ considerably less from the normal.* If the antiscorbutic dose provided is 0.5—0.7 of the minimum protective dose, an irregular dentin is formed with Tomes' canals in most places, but in the lingual part of the pulp there are found in some symmetric places ridges of a hard tissue, with the character of bone and lacking dentinal

canals. In this pulpa bone as well as in the newly formed irregular dentin, there are canals of Havers' type and isolated bone corpuscles which may be considered to consist of transformed odontoblasts. (Fig. 25—27.)

With an antiscorbutic dose of 0.8 or more of the minimum protective dose, the picture here described is changed so far, that there is no pulpa bone, but all the newly formed hard tissue in the pulpa consists of osteodentin (Fig. 28, 29), or even dentin (the first formed layer).

The endosmal bone formation.

A new interpretation is given of the changes found by earlier investigators in man and monkey, which correspond to those found in guinea-pig by the present author.

FRAENKEL has described and drawn the roof of the orbit in a child suffering from scurvy. He shows how the side of the bone next to cerebrum seems normal, with vigorous bone lamellæ, parallel mutually and with the surface, while the surface towards the orbit looks quite different. Instead of the vigorous columns, parallel with the surface, here we find slender columns standing at right angles; the illustration which is given bears a striking resemblance to Fig. 10. The periosteum is thin, and instead of lymphoid marrow there is framework marrow. HART and LESSING describe the condition of the lower jaw of monkeys suffering from scurvy. They make »die interessante und wichtige Feststellung, dass auch am Unterkiefer Veränderungen nachzuweisen sind. Die Corticalis des Unterkiefers bietet ein ganz zerfressenes und zernagtes Bild» — »ein verwittertes Aussehen. Die Auflösung des Knochens erfolgt aber nicht nur von aussen, sondern namentlich auch von den Haverschen Kanälchen, die breit eröffnet sind, in denen ein feines zellarmes fibrilläres Gewebe wuchert.» In all their cases periosteal hemorrhage was present. They also report »die poröse, zerfressene Aussenfläche des Schädeldaches». The descriptions of earlier authors are summarized thus by Hart and Lessing: »Die Bildung jungen periostalen

Knochengewebes ist von BARLOW, BAGINSKY, SCHMORL, SCHOEDEL und FRAENKEL gesehen worden, und von letzteren drei Authoren auch mikroskopisch studiert worden. Über die von Schoedel geäußerte Ansicht, dass diese Knochenneubildung keine primäre Erscheinung sei, vielmehr in die Reihe der Heilungsprozessen in weiterem Sinne gehören, herrscht volle Einigkeit.» HART and LESSING agree with this interpretation and attach special importance to the hemorrhages, which KOCH had already done. The investigators of recent years who have occupied themselves with the jaw in guinea-pig scurvy, characterize the jaw simply as »decalcified» (HOWE, TOWERUD, ROBB etc.).

I have studied the endosmal bone formation above all in the sections before mentioned under the heading of »Teeth». My pictures (see Fig. 10, 33, 34) recall those described by the investigators just named, more especially FRAENKEL, and HART and LESSING. The number of my cases being large, it is obvious that these changes — osteoporosis in the jaw, new formation of a porous, spongy bone on the surface instead of the usual, compact — are constant, as soon as the scurvy has reached a certain degree. In all cases where scorbutic changes have been manifest in the epiphyses of the long bones, they are also evident in the jaw. The new formation of this spongy bone is by no means uniform, it reaches its maximum in the lower ridge into which the roots of the molars penetrate. The new formation of this bone is on the section seen to begin along a straight line. In most sections there is no periosteal hemorrhage. The marrow is frame-work marrow, very deficient in cells. Stained with hematoxylin-eosin this spongy bone turns blue and is calcified. In cases where the bone formation seems to have stopped, it shows pictures of resorption with »osteoclasts» (Fig. 34).

A bone of the same appearance will sometimes be formed, when some special reason sets in for increased activity of the periosteum in the diaphyses of the long bones. This is, for instance, the case when, as sometimes happens, a fractured bone

wall has been thrust into the marrow cavity and the periosteum forms a bone of the above mentioned character on the outside. (Fig. 35, 43, 45.)

Thus the endosomal bone formation in scurvy of an early stage seems quantitatively as well as qualitatively to be reduced. From this there follows in the first place an osteoporosis, the more pronounced the more the scurvy has advanced, and with that a new formation of a calcified bone of spongy character, which is seen especially in certain definite sites (places of rapid growth) and which grows more slowly and gets more porotic the further the process advances.

The enchondral bone formation.

The detailed descriptions by earlier investigators of the scorbutic changes in the epiphyses of the long bones are quoted, especially in such portions that have been interpreted in a new manner by the author's own research and have now for the first time got an acceptable explanation. Already from those descriptions it may be supposed, what is confirmed through this research, that in scurvy a bone is formed enchondrally which is less differentiated than the normal bone and of a quite dissimilar character. This bone has been described by some investigators without further explanations, by others it has been interpreted as necrotizing after fracture, by others again, and this is the general explanation of recent years, as fibrin.

The macroscopic changes are described by SCHMORL and FRAENKEL in the following words: »Verarmung der Diaphysenden an Knochensubstanz, Verbreitung der präparatorischen Verkalkungszone.« Further particulars are given by HART and LESSING: »Die schmale und scharfe weissgraue Linie der präparatorischen Verkalkungszone sehen wir ersetzt durch eine wechselnd breite, diaphysenwärts nicht ganz scharfe, weissgraue Zone von mürbem, morschem Aussehen, von dem Schoedel sagt, man habe beim Zufühlen mit der Messerspitze die Empfindung, als wenn sie aus lauter kleinen kalkhaltigen Körnern bestände.«

I give the following extracts from descriptions by some

authors of the microscopic changes in this preparatory calcification zone.

JACOBSTHAL 1900:

»Als neuer Bestandtheil treten schmale, unregelmässig umgrenzte, bucklige, verkalkte Bälkchen auf. Sie sind stalaktitenähnlich, anastomosieren zum Theil; fast durchweg sind sie vollständig kalkhaltig.« Sometimes the central parts are colourless. Uncalcified substance is only met with in a few places and to a small extent. »Die Verkalkung ist eine homogene. In ihrem Innern erhalten die beschriebenen Gebilde Knochenkörperchen, die etwas grösser und plumper gebaut sind als die des normalen Knochens, doch zeigen sie bei Luft-Injection ziemlich reichliche, zum Theil anastomosierende feine Fortsätze.«

SCHOEDEL (1900) has described in an exceedingly clear and apt manner the changes seen in cases of scurvy in infants within the bone formation zone of the long bones. He has also proved that the strange formations to be seen there, are bones. This demonstration of his seems to have been forgotten, as ASCHOFF and KOCH do not appear to know it. On the other hand, Schoedel's explanation is less plausible when he declares the unusual character of the bone to be a necrosis consequent of fracture, at the same time stating that a fracture is not always present. The description is found *l. c.* pp. 33, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 44, 56, 57, 62, 63, 64, 65, 79, 85, 93, 98, 104, 111, 112, 122, 133, 134, and 135. It may be summed up thus:

Next to the cartilage proliferation zone there follows a wide greywhite zone, which under the point of the knife gives the impression of consisting in nothing but small grains of calcium. In this zone there are seen a large number of bone columns, often irregularly layered, often transversely. They are bulky, thick, massive, and their majority is seen subperiosteally. Often processes, or a network of processes, continue from these columns well into the marrow. These bone columns show none or few bone corpuscles. Often remaining calcified cartilage substance is seen in their centre. Schoedel regards these bone columns as more or less necrotic and believes the necrosis to be a consequence of the fracture which »*in most cases*« can be observed.

These columns are often connected with a tissue of a different appearance which Schoedel describes in the following manner:

»In mit Hämalun-Eosin gefärbten Präparaten ist eine eigentümliche, glänzend rubinroth gefärbte schollige Substanz auffällig. Sie ist immer im Anschluss an Knochen- oder Kalkbälkchen zu finden, u. z. liegt sie dann stets innerhalb der die Bälkchen umgebenden Osteoidsäume. *Fast immer*¹ sind diese Schollen an Stellen gelagert wo anscheinend Fracturen oder Zertrümmerungen solcher Bälkchen eingetreten sind. Hier und da findet man auch, der fraglichen Substanz benachbart, blassbläulich oder blassrosa, schmutzig verwaschen gefärbte Schollen, die ebenfalls in osteoide Substanz eingeschlossen sind. Ein Bild machte besonderen Eindruck: Ein kleines von einem breitem Osteoidsaum umgebenes Knochenbälkchen ist in der Mitte quer gebrochen, die beiden Enden sind etwas an einander vorbeigeglitten, ohne jedoch dabei den Osteoidsaum zu durchbrechen, und jedes trägt nun eine kleine Haube dieser rubinroth gefärbten, glänzenden, scholligen Substanz.»

»Wahrscheinlich handelt es sich um verändertes Knochengewebe, welches nicht selten allmählich in diese Substanz übergeht. Zuweilen sind Knochenkörperchen darin enthalten, deren Kerne mangelhaft gefärbt sind. Auffällig ist das gehäufte Auftreten fraglicher Massen in den seitlichen Partien des Schnittes.»

»Osteoide Substanz ist nicht mit den rubinroth gefärbten Stellen zu verwechseln, da sie nur eine zarte Hellrosa-Färbung angenommen hat.»

»Grosse, schon mit der Lupe bequem erkennbare, unregelmässig gestaltete, bei schwacher Vergrößerung structurlose, meist gleichmässig roth gefärbte schollige Massen — — — es laufen von ihnen bandförmige Ausläufer aus. — — — Damit dürfen in der gleichen Zone gelegene Gewebelücken nicht verwechselt werden, die mit einem feinflockigen, schwach roth gefärbten Inhalt ausgefüllt sind und die offenbar nichts anderes als Gerinnungsmassen darstellen.»

Schoedel has the impression that this homogeneous tissue, stained ruby red with eosin, consists of transformed calcified cartilage or bone columns. In epicrises and discussion he does not speak about them, but emphasizes that the disturbances in the bone formation are »weniger leicht verständlich». In

¹ The italics are mine.

summarizing he indicates them as being a »Hemmung, ja vielleicht ein Stillstand der Ossification«.

HART and LESSING, 1913:

»Angrenzend an die verkalkte Knorpelgrundsubstanz finden wir zunächst nun ganz kurze, auffallend plumpe und dünne, nun gelegentlich kleine Reste verkalkter Grundsubstanz einschliessende Knochengebilde ohne jede Orientierung der Lagerung, meist quer zur Knochenachse, und dazwischen allenthalben Herde krümeliger rötlichblauer Massen, die wohl nichts anders als zerfallende Kalkbälkchen darstellen. Den Knochenbälkchen fehlt grossentheils ein deutliches Osteoblastenlager, und wo Osteoblasten nachweisbar sind, sind sie niedrig.«

»Die Blutmasse traumatischer Blutungen bildet, wenn sie älter ist, zusammen mit nekrotisiertem Gewebe und einem Kalkdetritus jene eigentümlichen, fibrinösen Massen, von denen SCHMORL zuerst berichtet hat. Auch wenn sie keine grössere Trümmer von Kalkbälkchen einschliessen, haben wir ihnen Riesenzellen, zuweilen in beträchtlicher Anzahl, anliegen sehen, dagegen ist es uns manchmal selbst an offenbar recht alten derartigen Herden aufgefallen, dass keine Zeichen von Pigmentbildung wahrzunehmen waren.«

»Wenn JACOBSTHAL aus dem Gerüstmark unregelmässige Knochenbälkchen entstehen lässt, so müssen wir demgegenüber schon hier erwähnen, dass im floriden Stadium der Möller-Barlowschen Krankheit dem im Diaphysenmark wachsendem Gewebe, also dem Gerüstmark, die Fähigkeit der Knochenbildung vollständig abgeht. Nur im Heilungsstadium begegnen wir ihr.«

INGIER (1913) speaks, in a description of the changes in the primary calcification zone of scorbutic guinea-pig ribs, about bone splinters, lying embedded within a homogeneously coloured, structureless mass. This is mentioned in many places, and she seems to look upon it as consisting of fibrin, detritus etc. She points out as remarkable that the bone splinters embedded in this mass do not show any apposition, and sums up the bone changes as an atrophy of the bone with completely arrested bone formation.

ASCHOFF and KOCH (1919) describe this eosinophile mass in the calcification zone as fibrin.

»Das Trümmerfeld ist regelmässig gegen den Knorpel zu durch Fibrin abgedeckt, welches sich sofort einstellt, auch wenn der kleinste Bruch besteht, und sich als Schutzschicht zwischen Knochen-

trümmer und Knorpel einschleibt. Dass dieser Schutz des Knorpels gegen Reibung die Hauptaufgabe des Fibrins zu sein scheint, zeigen alle mikroskopischen Präparate mit grosser Regelmässigkeit. Man sieht durchweg, wie nur die Knorpelseite der Knochentrümmer, soweit kleinere Splitten nicht ganz in den Fibrinmassen liegen, von dem Fibrin bedeckt wird. Letzteres pflegt sich auffallend stark mit Eosin zu färben, enthält nur selten Blutbeimengung, ist vielfach stark hyalinisiert und kann natürlich auch Zeichen der Organisation aufweisen». (P. 89.)

»Woher dieses Fibrin kommt, ist nicht leicht zu entscheiden, da es nicht den Anschein hat, als ob es aus grösseren Blutungen in dem Bruchspalt stammte; sonst müsste unter den vielen zur Untersuchung gelangten Rippen¹, die alle Stadien der Frakturierung umfassen, sich sicher auch solche gefunden haben, wo man neben Fibrin noch frisches Blut in grösseren Mengen im Bruchspalt liegen sieht. Das ist aber durchaus nicht der Fall, sondern Blutungen im Bruchspalt treten ganz zurück. Nur kleine Reihen roter Blutkörperchen sieht man in einzelnen Fällen in das Fibrinnetz eingeschaltet.» (P. 85.)

From page 54 to page 80 in the authors' record of cases, the description of this »fibrin» is met with on every page, and the investigation has been accepted by Hess, who quotes it in several places, just concerning the »fibrin» (*l. c.* p. 106, 108, 109).

HERZOG (1921) describes similar pictures in guinea-pigs as ASCHOFF and KOCH of »rötlich gefärbte, auch Fibrinfärbung gebende, nekrotische Massen zwischen dem Knochen und Knorpel». He altogether agrees with the opinion of the above-mentioned authors that these masses are fibrin, acting as a kind of protection.

Against this interpretation IWABUCHI, in 1922, makes a cautious opposition: »Die Ansicht von Aschoff und Koch, dass die Fibrinmassen als Schutzschicht des Knorpels gegen die Reibungen der freien Knochentrümmer aufzufassen sind, trifft wohl nicht für alle Fälle zu, denn ich fand Fibrin, einige zarten Knorpelspannen der enchondralen Ossifikationszone umhüllend auch dann, wenn es noch nicht zur Kontinuitätstrennung und Trümmerfeldbildung gekommen war».

¹ In all, 14.

Several of the authors mentioned lay stress upon the difficulties of interpreting the pictures described in this manner. These difficulties specially arise in the explaining of the strongly eosinophile coloured columns or masses which connect cartilage and bone (SCHOEDEL), or are seen in layers on the surface of the bone bridges which faces the cartilage (ASCHOFF and KOCH), or completely enclose splinters of normal bone (INGIER a. o.).—SCHOEDEL's explanation of them as being bone, necrotizing as a consequence of fracture, fails through the fact that there sometimes is no fracture (ASCHOFF and KOCH, IWABUCHI, the present author). Aschoff and Koch who call the formation in question fibrin are not able to explain from where this fibrin may have come.

As a result of studies of more than 1 000 ribs and a large number of the other long bones from guinea-pigs suffering from scurvy, I am able to give another explanation which solves the difficulties. In the majority of these ribs there are formations like those described above, and a detailed description would largely be a repetition of the quotations I have given (Fig. 35—48). My investigation shows that the formation in question, as Schoedel moreover has already proved, is *bone*. That this bone gives fibrin colour, is not surprising, as it has this quality in common with all other bone. The fibrin colouring is not specific. In the sections I have been able to follow the forming of this bone in its different phases. In early stages it is seen like a net of somewhat irregular columns to join the cartilage columns with the normal bone bridges. They show canaliculi, even though these are fewer in number and not so regular as normally. In later stages the formative power seems to be lost more and more, and the osteoblasts, now spool-shaped and slender, surround almost structureless masses, in which only some few canals with an enclosed cell or red blood corpuscle suggest bone structure (Fig. 37—40). These masses are often connected both with the normal bone columns and with the calcified cartilage columns, which, in conformity with FRAENKEL's description, grow further inwards than normally. Sometimes we see, between the eosinophile

bone and the cartilage columns, columns of basophile bone, in the centres of which the primarily calcified beams of the cartilage remain. A darker colouring of an added surface layer and the elongated cells (osteoblasts) next to this, justify in some measure the term of bone (Fig. 43). Finally there are seen in some cases, as ASCHOFF and KOCH have described, decaying granulous masses without structure. These are probably to be considered as a secretion product of the now impotent osteoblasts, a last desperate attempt at bone formation. At last all ossification stops, and all the different kinds of bone now described become subject to resorption.

With regard to the chemical conditions of this bone, we have shown on sections prepared by grinding of not decalcified ribs, with side light according to SONNENBURG, that it is here a question of calcified tissue. The same thing appears from staining with silver, according to v. KOSSA (Fig. 41), and from radiograms (Fig. 42), taken by Dr. Å. ÅKERLUND, which show the pathognomonic appearance, first described by FRAENKEL, of a dense shadow in the preparatory calcification zone, shading off linearly towards the epiphysis, diffusely towards the diaphysis.

By staining the collagen substance according to HANSEN it is shown that this bone, formed in the course of scurvy, lacks collagen fibrils. (Plates 1 and 2.) While the collagen assumes a beautiful red colour with this staining, the bone in question turns yellow, in the same manner as the precollagen in embryonal bone tissue. In the cartilage the collagen in scurvy is considerably weaker than normally.

An other sign indicating the abnormal character of the scorbutic bone is that rests of the preparatorily calcified cartilage substance, which has not been organized, remains for a long time visible in the bone columns. This has already been pointed out by SCHOEDEL a. o.

The enchondral bone formed in the course of scurvy thus differs from the normal bone chiefly in the following points:

1. The osteoblasts more and more assume the appearance of elongated connective tissue cells.

2. The regular form of the normal bone and its general organisation are lacking.

3. The typical bone structure, with bone corpuscles and canaliculi, becomes less and less apparent; instead of that there is a general homogenization of columns and masses.

4. Collagen fibrils are absent.

Among the circumstances which have seemed to earlier investigators difficult of explanation, but which well agree with the interpretation given here, I may mention the following:

That »Knochenkörperchen» (SCHOEDEL) are seen in the eosinophile tissue in question.

That this tissue is always seen in connection with bone or cartilage (SCHOEDEL) and that it most frequently covers the portion of the columns which is turned towards the cartilage (ASCHOFF and KOCH).

That this tissue is seen between cartilage and normal bone even where there is no fracture (IWABUCHI). ASCHOFF and KOCH also found that 2 of the 14 ribs investigated were without fracture, and in one of these two they saw the so-called fibrin formation.

That fissures traverse this tissue (HART and LESSING).

That in cases of coincident rickets this tissue was always found enclosed in osteoid seams (SCHOEDEL).

That it is fretted by giant-cells (HART and LESSING, a. o.); this is a question of resorption pictures.

That it lacks pigment (HART and LESSING), which would be unaccountable if we suppose, like those authors, that it originates from hemorrhage.

That bone columns enclosed in such masses always lack apposition-picture (INGIER); this is natural, as these masses themselves constitute the apposed bone tissue.

That this inferior bone is most frequently found where there is a fracture, is explained by the circumstance that, in a certain stage of scurvy, the ribs — for it is chiefly in the ribs that this coincidence is observed — are nearly all fractured, as already HOLST and FRÖLICH have noted in 1912. In the other long bones the tissue described is seen more frequently

in unfractured bone. Even in ribs I have observed the same thing in several cases. Where the fracture occurs, it is probably in certain cases partly due to such inferior bone having replaced the normal bone. For example, see Fig. 43, where the fracture has occurred unusually high up in the diaphysis, and just in an accumulation of that kind of bone. If, which is possible, a fracture can call forth a formation of this special bone as a callus formation, surely the relation of cause and effect can also be the opposite: the fracture occurs in consequence of the qualitative as well as quantitative inferiority of the bone formed in the course of scurvy.

The rows of red blood-corpuscles that ASCHOFF and KOCH have seen in the »fibrin net», seem to have been capillaries between the bone bridges.

Aschoff and Koch, as well as Hart and Lessing, also have illustrations which as far as they go — though not so well as the descriptions — confirm the conception that is expressed in these pages.

It also agrees well with the interpretation quoted, that, as H. WINBERGER has found in 1922 by Roentgen-examining scurvy patients, »die mächtigen Schattenkeulen an den distalen Femurmetaphysen an ihren epiphysären Rand eine enchondrale Ossification im Sinne eines normalen Längenwachstums zeigen»; that is, the direct connection of the shapeless bone masses formed in scurvy with the preliminarily calcified columns of the cartilage, displayed in the histological sections by Schoedel and the present author, has been stated by Winberger already during life by aid of Roentgen rays. Winberger did not pronounce on the importance of his discovery in his preliminary communication.

The microscopic changes, about which I have entered into particulars here, are situated in the preparatory calcification zone and the so-called »Trümmerfeld area». With regard to the macroscopic appearance of this zone, »the white line» and the formation of a typical rosary, as well as the occurrence of the frame-work marrow or »Gerüstmark» and of a general osteoporosis all through the long bones in scurvy, these changes,

as earlier writers have described them, have also been constant in my cases and are most marked in the 2nd—8th pairs of ribs. Concerning these I will therefore only enter into one small detail.

ASCHOFF and KOCH write in their records of cases (p. 80) — speaking of the rib in which no fracture could be discovered: »Bei der 6:ten Rippe verdient noch hervorgehoben zu werden, dass sich *im Fugenwinkel an der Aussenseite*¹ unter dem Perichondrium Fibrinauflagerung findet und dass auf dieser umschriebenen Stelle das Knochenmark zellärmer aussieht». The case in question is an early stage of scurvy. This most frequent site of the first scorbutic change in the bone marrow and bone (Fig. 37, 44, 45) is described by several authors ever since HOLST and FRÖLICH in 1912 (see Fig. 3 in their work), who explicitly associate it with the quicker growth in this place. The parallelism between the formation of frame-work marrow and pathological bone, of which Aschoff and Koch give such a good example, I have found constant in all my scorbutic guinea-pigs. The more the bone marrow loses its specific character, the less the osteoblasts also resemble the normal, and the more pathological the new bone becomes till finally the bone formation ceases. It seems to me most natural to consider this a matter of co-ordinate changes of bone marrow cells and bone cells.

How the inferior bone formed in scurvy develops when the disease is remedied, is found from Series 17, animals 75—78, Figures 45, 46, and Plates 1 and 2. Animal 75 died of scurvy and showed great changes in its bones with abundant formation of scorbutic bone (Fig. 45 a and b, Plate 1). The other three animals in the series also had severe scurvy, but the day before the death of the first they were given a dose of orange juice and recovered. After a month they were killed. The bone picture is seen from Fig. 46 a and b, and Plate 2. The osteoblast layer has resumed its normal appearance, so has the bone marrow. The cartilage columns have not yet become fully arranged. The bone columns consist for

¹ The italics are mine.

the most part of newly formed bone, differing from the normal in a certain bulkiness of structure and in having strong bone columns running transversely, just like the scorbutic eosinophile columns. Remains of these are seen, some lying between the new columns, in which case a strong resorption seems to take place, some lying enclosed within them. That it takes a long time before the calcification zone in scurvy altogether returns to the normal state, has been proved by Roentgen examinations of children (FRAENKEL, FRANK). Still 17 months after the clinical recovery, scurvy could be diagnosed in the radiogram. It is important in such examinations, however, that attention should be paid to the antiscorbutic dose given, in order to make sure that there is a complete recovery and not only a passing of the scurvy from a manifest to a latent stage, as is possibly the case in Series 17.

Cartilage.

The atrophic changes in scurvy of the proliferating zone of the cartilage are well known after the descriptions of previous investigators. As a new thing I have in scurvy cases found a collagen atrophy in the cartilage. This collagen atrophy is especially marked in the columns of the proliferating zone and in their neighbourhood. The sections stained with methylenblue do not indicate any difference from the normal in regard to chondroitin-sulfuric acid.

Four cases of infantile scurvy.

The conception of the bone structure in scurvy which has been pronounced above after experiments on guinea-pigs, I have been able to corroborate by reference to descriptions and illustrations by earlier writers on the pathology of scurvy in infant and adults, in guinea-pig and monkey. I have also had the opportunity myself of studying a large number of sections from 8 cases of scurvy in the first and second year

of life, examined *post-mortem*, prepared and described by Professor U. QUENSEL in 1898. Professor Quensel has most kindly handed over the material, which later on will be published by us more exhaustively, to enable me to communicate some extracts.

Four of these cases belong to the 15 cases of morbus Barlow, recorded by MEDIN at the Northern Congress for Medicine in Kristiania 1899. An abstract of Medin's lecture is to be found in Norsk Mag. f. Laegevid., 59, 1899, p. 1016. The following extract may be quoted:

»A similar disease has not been described from the Allmänna Barnhuset during the late 55 years, when the first case occurred in January 1898. The second followed in June, and during the whole year in all 5 cases. During January—May 1899, 10 cases appeared. The age of the patients was $\frac{1}{2}$ — $1\frac{1}{2}$ year. They were all weak children, fed with cow's milk, *all of them with chronic intestinal catarrhs*. Twelve of the children had rachitis, two lues. The first symptom was the change in the general condition, the complexion becoming greyish pale. The children lay still, displayed tenderness when touched. The extremities were swollen, especially at the epiphyses. Hemorrhages in the muscles, periosteum, and gums, even before dentition. Four cases led to death.» (*Post-mortem* record, see below.)

MEDIN agrees with the English and Americans that morbus Barlow is infantile scurvy. The differences extant are explained by the anatomical and physiological circumstances in the growth of the child. Medin points out, that out of his 15 cases 3 lacked clinical signs of rickets. Of these 3, one had been carefully examined patho-anatomically without any trace of rickets being found.

The general death rate in 1897—1898 among the children at the Allmänna Barnhuset is said to have been lower than at any earlier period. The milk had since 1887 been sterilized with Soxhlet's apparatus. In this manner 5—6 000 children had been fed without any scurvy appearing previously. During the last years the children had been given Mellin's food, up to 8 teaspoonfuls a day, and milk-sugar. The treatment consisted of administering the juice of $\frac{1}{2}$ —1 lemon daily.

Among these 8 cases, of which patho-anatomical examination has been made, rather exhaustive records have now been

found concerning 4, from which records extracts are given in Part V.

These records show beyond doubt that the four children were suffering from infantile scurvy. In four more children who during the same time had died in the Allmänna Barnhuset from intercurrent diseases, Quensel found typical scorbutic changes which I have studied in his microscopical sections, Fig. 49—51. Quensel's exceedingly careful histological examination allows us to follow the formation of scorbutic bone in its different phases. First the bone cells lose their canaliculi. Then the bone cells themselves become scarce, and a homogeneous calcified bone is formed, in which there are few or no corpuscles. In cases complicated with rickets, the osteoid tissue shows the same structural changes towards a structureless tissue. Even in small details, such as the higher degree of the rib changes on the outer, convex side, and the first formation of the scorbutic bone occurring in the »Fugenwinkel», the changes present in Quensel's cases correspond to those found by me in guinea-pigs.

When, in an institution with uniform dietary for a large number of persons, cases of manifest scurvy appear, it is generally found on closer investigation that many of the others also show symptoms that may be suspected to be of scorbutic nature. In order to investigate whether this was the case in the Allmänna Barnhuset at the end of the nineties, I have closely gone over the cases described by QUENSEL in his book of 1899. Quensel has brought together extracts from clinical and *post-mortem* records about 144 children, mainly in the three last quarters of the first year of their life, who died during the time June 1895—October 1897 and were examined by him from a different point of view (the presence of bacteria in various organs). The scorbutic symptom which is most easily identified subsequently is the hemorrhagic diathesis, and I have tried to ascertain the presence of this symptom. I found that, out of the 144 children, 73 showed hemorrhages during the last months of their lives or at the *post-mortem* examination. The organs which have been affected have been the follow-

ing (I leave out of consideration one case, which has been diagnosed as scorbus infantilis and stands as No. 1 among those reported above): dura mater as a pachymeningitis hemorrhagica interna 37 times, cerebrum 1, lungs 23, pleura 7, pericardium 2, palate 1, tonsils 1, oesophagus 1, ventricle 1, intestine 11, cutis and subcutis 17, middle ear 3, kidneys 3, ureters and bladder 4, conjunctiva palpebrar. 1, lymphoglandulæ mesent. 1; besides, blood was found during life in fæces 7 times, urine 4, vomits 1, secretion from nose 6. Blood in the renal canals was found 7 times at the microscopical examination. — In all 139 localizations.

All the 144 children in question had infections and in a large number of cases culture of bacteria, in most cases streptococci, was made with inoculation on animals. Only 2 cases formed a basis for assuming that the bacteria were actually hemorrhagiparous. In both cases it was a question of bacillus pyocyaneus, which caused intestinal hemorrhages in rabbit.

I certainly do not intend to express as my opinion that scurvy in *every* case should have been the cause of the hemorrhages here mentioned. In some cases (QUENSEL'S Cases 12, 60, 84), however, it is possible with great probability to draw the conclusion that clinically fully developed but unidentified *manifest* scurvy has been present. For the majority of the remaining cases the supposition of an otherwise latent scurvy seems to be the natural explanation of such a frequent hemorrhagic diathesis (50%). From this we might conclude that the cow's milk which was given in the Allmänna Barnhuset during this time was scorbutogenetic. The appearance of a series of manifest cases, as recorded by MEDIN, is partly explained through this, but to make the explanation complete we require the evidence of a circumstance, likely to aggravate the scurvy in these cases. This circumstance is given in Medin's information that all the children, who had manifest scurvy, suffered from chronic enterocatarrhs. From many different quarters it has been pointed out that these catarrhs often call forth an outbreak of scurvy, both in children and adults (see p. 117). It may also be remarked that SCHOEDEL (l. c., p. 119)

considers Mellin's food to have contributed to the appearance of scurvy in one of his five cases. Of this food the children in the Allmänna Barnhuset were given up to 8 tea-spoonfuls a day.

Summary and conclusions concerning the scorbutic bone formation.

Concerning the bone formation in scurvy, HOLST and FRÖLICH write in 1912: »Eine Apposition von normalem Knochengewebe scheint ganz zu fehlen». About a formation of pathological bone they say nothing. HESS summarizes in 1920 the investigations undertaken up to that time thus: »In scurvy osteoblastic bone growth is greatly inhibited, but what growth does take place occurs in a normal and orderly manner». The investigation reported above shows this conception to be wrong.

Before the total cessation of growth after a guinea-pig has been put on absolutely scorbutic diet, at least two, often four weeks elapse. During this time a less differentiated bone is formed in teeth as well as in endosmal bones and the epiphyses of the long tubular bones. This pathologic bone can be seen in the teeth already during the course of the second week, in the lower jaw and ribs during the third week. If there is any antiscorbutic contents in the food, the formation of this bone goes on for a longer time and it gains a larger extent. The bone-forming cells change in appearance. The odontoblasts take the character of osteoblasts, the osteoblasts grow more and more like spool-shaped connective-tissue cells. In the teeth and the lower jaw the new pathological bone has, instead of the ordinary, compact, a spongy, porous character. Also the diaphyses of the long bones become porous. At the epiphyseal junctions, on the other hand, shapeless, dense column masses are formed instead of the slender spongy net-work of bone. In teeth and lower jaw the pathological bone contains collagen fibrils even though they are less developed than in normal bone; in the new columns of the long bones collagen substance is lacking. This pathological bone is everywhere calcified. There is no evidence for the *bone*

tissue, as such, having an altered proportion of calcium. Per weight unit, however, the *bone* becomes more or less calciferous according to its structure, as compact bone holds more calcium per weight unit than does spongy bone. In the dental bone TOVERUD, in the porotic rib BARDT and EDELSTEIN have proved this lessened calcium proportion. In the growth-zone of the long bones, FRAENKEL a. o. have found an increased calcium proportion by means of Roentgen examination. This is only explained satisfactorily through the author's analysis of the bone masses formed in this place by scurvy.

If the scorbutic process goes further, all bone formation ceases. The resorption, which, in the bone formed before the onset of scurvy, seems to have an ordinary extent, is seen to take place more rapidly in the bone formed in the course of scurvy, and there it gives pictures, which are similar in teeth, lower jaw and long tubular bones (Fig. 14, 34, 47 all from No. 1).

If, on the other hand, after the formation of scorbutic bone the animal receives some antiscorbutic, the osteoblasts and odontoblasts may regain their appearance and a rapid reorganization begin, which in No. 75 is evident after one day. In the tooth the reorganized dental bone gets a special character, of an irregular dentin with some few Havers' canals — osteodentin. In the connective-tissue bone hardly any difference can be seen between the reorganized bone and that formed before scurvy set in, but separating them there is a line of demarcation, staining blue with hematoxylin, in which the different bone layers often are detached when the sections are made. In the ribs, finally, parts of the pathologic bone columns are subjected to resorption, while on the base of some others new columns are formed of very nearly normal appearance.

The vascular changes observable in the bone system are described in connection with the vascular changes in other organs. Here I will only touch upon one point. HESS writes: »A marked distinction between scurvy and rickets is the paucity of blood-vessels in the cartilaginous area and in the mar-

row in scurvy, compared with the increased vascularity so generally encountered in rickets». This statement is true only with regard to the very ossification line and the adjacent portion of the marrow, and only for an advanced stage of scurvy. In the initial stage, I have found, on the other hand, and this also appears from a closer study of the records of earlier investigators, a constant hyperemia in the ossification zone, as well as in the tooth pulp. After a frame-work marrow has become formed here, the hyperemia disappears, but remains in the marrow of the diaphysis. With this statement the hypothesis must disappear, which after SCHMORL has been repeated by nearly all later investigators in this matter, that the paucity of vessels in the growth-zone should be the cause of the bone changes, more especially of the deficient melting of the preliminarily calcified cartilage.

This investigation having established the formation of a pathological bone in scurvy, the hypothesis brought out by ASCHOFF and KOCH in 1919 is no longer valid, that in scurvy the bone-forming cells would be able to form a normal bone, but that the material required, some supposed colloid cement substance, would be lacking. *Instead it is evident that the deficient bone formation is caused by a degeneration, or rather a receding of the bone-forming cells, these being changed so as to form a qualitatively more and more degenerate as well as quantitatively more and more reduced bone, till their activity eventually ceases altogether.*

My interpretation of the bone formation in scurvy, in which stress is laid upon the importance that must be attached to the gradually sinking activity of the bone cells, also makes away with several rather ill-balanced hypotheses concerning this field of investigation. So the attempts of SCHMORL a. o. to explain through entirely outward circumstances (compression) the appearance of the cartilage proliferation zone. So DELF and TOZER's supposition, accepted even by MACCALLUM, that the transversal bone column that in certain chronic mitigated cases — in fact a consequence of deficient growth and a decreasing formative power of the osteoblasts — is seen to

run along the edge of the cartilage, would itself cause the cessation of the bone formation. So the same two authors' hypothesis that this bone beam would be an attempt on the part of nature to strengthen the more and more brittle junction of cartilage and bone. Besides, it is evident that a transversally placed bone column hardly can be fit to keep together the loosening pieces of bone and cartilage, especially as the fracture is generally located a little bit closer to the diaphysis than is the beam mentioned. In order to serve this purpose a beam ought to have been placed longitudinally over the fissure.

These hypotheses, as well as that of ASCHOFF and KOCH mentioned above, about a protecting effect of the supposed fibrin, are examples of how doubtful teleological explanations often are allowed to do service instead of an unravelling of uncertain questions through continued study.

The changes of the bone cells and the bone marrow are common to the various types of bone formed in scurvy. For the rest I wish to point out the resemblance between the structure of the new bone in the pulp, lower jaw and the periosteally formed bone of the long bones. (Fig. 10, 33, 35.)

It is noteworthy that in this receding of the higher specific functions, the result is a product that in certain respects strikingly reminds us of embryonic formations (Fig. 32 and 48). Such is the case with the frame-work marrow, with the long-remaining calcified cartilage column in the preliminary calcification zone, with the spongy character of the new jaw-bone, and with certain of the changes in the teeth, as well as with the fact that the enchondrally new-formed bone lacks collagen substance and turns a yellow colour when stained according to Hansen. This circumstance is well worth a closer study.

CHAPTER II.

The skeleton musculature. (Fig. 52—65.)

Accounts of earlier investigators are summarized, criticized or confirmed. The presence in scurvy of a myopathy is proved, which consists in an atrophy with certain characteristic features.

About the symptomatology in adult scurvy HESS writes: »The earliest sign of scurvy is usually a change in the complexion of the individual — — — he loses his accustomed vigor, seemingly becomes indolent and complains of tiring quickly, and of breathlessness». This unwillingness to move in scorbutic patients has up till now been connected with hemorrhages into the musculature or with bone changes, and this both in man and in animal. As has already been set forth, a study of my guinea-pigs fed on scorbutic diet has given me the definite impression, that we have here to deal with a purely muscular symptom, a general weakness of muscle that manifests itself in the animal's movements. Even after some joint has begun to hurt or there has been some hemorrhages, it is not these changes which alone or even chiefly give the scorbutic guinea-pig its characteristic gait, but a marked slowness and sluggishness in the muscular movements. This increases till the end. An example of this extreme weakness of muscle is the manner of death which has befallen several of the scorbutic animals, *e. g.*, No. 48 and 54. They have been overlaid by their fellows. When guinea-pigs are kept several together in one cage, they lie down by night piled on the top of each other in a small pyramid. A healthy guinea-pig seems well to endure two and even three others lying over him. But the lessened tonus in the wall of the chest of scorbutic animals does not resist the pressure. The animal is perfectly flattened down and thus suffocated. Another example of muscle weakness is the death which befell the animals No. 87 and 121, that were drowned in the milk basin. The latter only had his muzzle in the basin and seems to have lacked strength for raising its head over the edge.

The pale yellow colour, the strange lardy appearance and the weakened consistence of scorbutic muscles have been pointed out by BARLOW, and by HART and LESSING. Other investigators describe the muscular changes only in connection with hemorrhages as a lemon coloured edema (SCHOEDEL) etc. A change, not before described in detail, located in the intercostal musculature, is mentioned on p. 30.

On the other hand we find several reports of the microscopical picture of the scorbutic muscle. LEVEN found (1871) changes in the sacrolumbar and intercostal musculature in scurvy patients. In the same year other French investigators, LASÈGUE and LEGROUX, and also Hayem, observed fatty degeneration, edema and atrophy in the truncal musculature, both in connection with hemorrhages and without. In 1900, JACOBSTHAL describes the muscular atrophy as a symptom of infantile scurvy. As one cause of this he mentions hemorrhages with ensuing edema of the musculature, but does not find this explanation sufficient and therefore attributes part of the effect to the inactivity. In 1905, SATO and NAMBU found in muscles from scurvy patients interstitial hemorrhage, atrophy and degeneration of the fibres, interstitial myositis.

In 1907, HOLST and FRÖLICH published their excellent investigations on guinea-pigs. They say: »We have further, in very many cases, examined the muscles of the limbs. *The fibres of these were to a large extent more slender than usual*¹ and many of them showed some fatty degeneration. *At the same time a larger or smaller number of them were often dissolved into rows of irregular hyaline dots*¹, which did not always stain in the same way as the unaltered fibres. *Between these dots there could be seen here and there small accumulations of the multiplied sarcolemma cells*¹, but otherwise no multiplication or immigration of cells could be discovered.» In their summary and conclusions, however, Holst and Frölich say nothing about these observations, nor have I seen them reported in the literature except by Jackson and Moore.

Hart and Lessing examined in 1913 the musculature in

¹ The italics are mine.

their 5 monkeys. They found distinct degenerative changes in the skeleton muscles. »Am auffallendsten jedoch ist die Ansammlung von massenhaften, farblosen, kristallinischen Körnchen in einzelnen aufgequollenen und degenerierten Muskelfasern, die sich bei Säurezusatz lösen und bei Färbung mit Hämatoxylin eine tiefblaue Farbe annehmen. Es handelt sich um feine Kalkkörnchen.« They found no connection between fatty degeneration and calcium deposits in the muscle fibres. They say: »Um einen allgemein verbreiteten Process handelt es sich sicher nicht«.

In 1919, ASCHOFF and KOCH's large work appeared which, however, with regard to the study of the musculature in scurvy does not signify any essential advance. Concerning the framework marrow they refute successfully, as INGIER a. o. had done earlier, LOOSER's conception that it would presuppose hemorrhages, whereas with regard to the muscular changes they maintain this very idea of the etiological importance of the hemorrhages. As HESS seems in his monograph to accept the conclusions of Aschoff and Koch in this respect, their account must be examined in greater detail.

First of all we must note that Aschoff and Koch say about their material (p. 45): »Von der Muskulatur wurde hauptsächlich die am meisten von Blutungen betroffene Beinmuskulatur untersucht und zwar auch hier die frischen wie die älteren Muskelblutungen«. It seems as if this limitation of the material deprived the authors' conclusions of all foundation with regard to the musculature where there had been *no* hemorrhage.

Further they say p. 45: »Man sieht im mikroskopischen Bild häufig von einem Blutnest zu dem anderen quer über die Muskelbündel hinüberziehende verbindende Blutstrassen, die den Eindruck machen, als wenn es sich um Blutauffüllung von in anderer Ebene liegenden Gewebsspalten handelte. Bei anderen Präparaten jedoch hat man den Eindruck, als wenn die über dem Muskelbündel verlaufenden Blutungen mit dem die Muskelfasern umspinnenden Kapillarnetz in Beziehung zu bringen sind. Auf Querschnitten sieht man, besonders in der Nähe der Faszie, öfters ausgedehnte Netzwerke von frischen

Blutungen, die jede einzelne Muskelfaser mit ihren Maschen einschneiden.» To this we may remark, that nothing is said about the hyperemia with maximally dilated vessels, frequently seen in the scorbutic muscle, and which often gives a picture like the one here described and also depicted by Aschoff and Koch (Fig. 19 in their work).

On page 46 they say: »Bei manchen Muskelfasern fällt wohl auf, dass sie sich auffallend dunkel mit Eosin färben, manche Muskelfasern sehen auch sehr viel schmaler und etwas kernreicher aus, doch hat man den Eindruck, dass es sich nur um Folgeerscheinungen infolge von Blutungen handelt». — »Schliesslich sei noch erwähnt, dass bei alten scorbutischen Muskelblutungen eine allgemeine Atrophie der Muskelfasern und eine beträchtliche Vermehrung des interstitiellen Bindegewebes beobachtet wird, Erscheinungen, die aber auf die allgemeine Kachexie und Inaktivitätsatrophie zu beziehen sind.»

The possibility that the atrophy, at least in part, might be scorbutic, is not taken into consideration. However, in the summary (p. 102) the authors do not express themselves in quite such a categorical manner. »Auch die Verfettung der Skelettmuskulatur hört nicht zum Bilde der Scorbut, sondern ist, wenn überhaupt vorhanden, durch andere Ursachen, besonders durch Zirkulationsstörungen infolge Thrombosen, zu erklären. Die Muskulatur bleibt dagegen trotz ausgedehnter Blutungen und Druck durch dieselben auffallend gut erhalten und zeigt nur stellenweise Atrophie, *wohl*¹ als Zeichen der Inaktivitätsatrophie, und *hier und da schmale junge Muskelfasern mit wuchernden Kernen.*»¹

HERZOG (1922) saw in scorbutic guinea-pigs a muscular degeneration, which in one case was very strong. She supposes, without seeming to be quite convinced, that this degeneration is caused by hemorrhages.

Already this abstract of the literature, and especially of Holst and Frölich's investigation, indicates the possibility of a primary atrophy of the musculature in scurvy. Holst and Frölich's work, however, is not unexceptionable on account of

¹ The italics are mine.

the incomplete basal diet. It has therefore seemed of importance to subject my material to a close histological examination with regard to the muscles. In most of the animals, sections have been examined from the lower end of brachium and thigh, upper and lower ends of forearm and bone, and from most costal interstices. In many cases, especially the higher numbers, only a few muscles have been examined, as shown by the records, it being considered unnecessary to extend the examination further. In general, the same sections have been used for the study of both muscular changes and bone changes.

The examined animals are divided into the following groups.

Group 1. Healthy animals without scurvy or infection. The numbers of these animals are given under the heading 6 on p. 38. The musculature shows a normal appearance, uniform colouring, fibres that are of uniform thickness.

Group 2. 23 animals with manifest scurvy without infection. 13 of these have a scorbut manifestus gravior (0 anti-scorbutic), No. 1, 3, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28, 35, 112, 113, 115. 10 have a scorbut manifestus mitior (m. pr. d. 0,1—0.2), No. 58, 59, 65, 67, 75, 83, 86, 88, 122, 123. The former had a lifetime of 19—38 days, the latter of 32—60 days.

All these animals show distinct, most of them very pronounced changes of the musculature. These changes may be described thus.

a) Hyperemia (100%). This is especially pronounced near the connections with tendons or periosteum, above all near the epiphyses. (Figs. 53, 54.)

b) Hemorrhages (100%). These are always localized, of limited extent and are chiefly seen in those places where the hyperemia is strongest. Often hemorrhage has only been met with in one or two places.

c) Changes within the muscle fibre (100%). (Fig. 55, 56, 57). The single fibrils show more clearly than in normal cases, often so distinctly that the muscle fibre as entity has disappeared. General slenderness of the muscle fibres especially near the connections with tendons or periosteum, and chiefly

near the epiphyses. Increased width of small sections of muscle fibres, which then also are homogeneous in those places, without either cross-striation or longitudinal striation, and stain dark red with eosin. These dark red, homogeneous sections are often as so-called muscle fractures seen in an otherwise tender muscle fibre. For the rest the cross-striation of these fibres is well preserved. Even in the calcified necroses of muscle fibre, described below, the cross-striation is sometimes marked through the calcium grains being layered in parallel disks.

d) Necroses of larger or smaller sections of muscle fibres or fasciculi (79% — all except No. 65, 67, 112, 122, 123). In 9 cases (39%) part of these necroses show depositions of grains and lumps, staining blue-grey with hematoxylin (calcium). (Fig. 58, 59, 60.)

e) Increased connective tissue (74%). The connective tissue is often seen as strands of rounded fibroblasts, rich in endoplasm, in the place of a necrotized muscle fibre. (Fig. 56, 60.)

f) Giant-cells of a special type (96% — all except Case 20). These cells have the appearance of big syncytial nuclei (see Fig. 55, 61, 62, 63), in connection with which there is but rarely a narrow zone of blue-coloured protoplasm. The nuclei, which always hang well together, may assume very different shapes. They stain diffusely a dark blue-black with hematoxylin. (About these, see further p. 76.)

Group 3. 5 animals without infection with scorbut latens levior, m. pr. d. 0.5—0.8, all 92 days. No. 144, 146, 151, 160, 161.

The muscle pictures are everywhere normal.

Group 4. 16 animals with infection and scorbut manifestus. 8 animals had scorbut gravior (0 antiscorbutic), 19—36 days, No. 49, 50, 54, 57, 116, 117, 118, 119, 8 animals had scorbut mitior, m. pr. d. 0.1—0.2, 17—58 days, No. 60, 66, 87, 121, 125, 127, 131, 132. Of the 16 animals, 7 were infected with tuberculosis.

All these animals showed the changes described under Group 2 a and c. The other changes described there were also found in certain animals of this group, in a percentage indicated in the table below. In the first row are the 9 animals without tuberculous infection, in the second the 7 animals with such.

Table 3.

	Scorbut manifestus with acute infection	Scorbut manifestus with tubercul.
Hemorrhages per cent.	56	43
Necroses » »	67	86
Calcium grains » »	33	71
Giant-nuclei cells » »	56	86
Increased connective tissue » »	67	100

Group 5. 23 animals with infection and scorbut latens. 2 animals, No. 29 and 30, with scorbut gravior, 12 and 14 days. 14 animals with scorbut latens extensus, m. pr. d. 0.1—0.5, 15—92 days, No. 18, 63, 120, 128, 129, 130, 135, 136, 138, 139, 140, 141, 148, 149. 7 animals with scorbut latens levior, min. pr. d. 0.5—0.8, 18—92 days, No. 145, 147, 150, 155, 156, 164, 165.

One of these animals, No. 29, 12 days, showed no muscular changes whatever. Another, No. 139, m. pr. d. 0.3, 77 days, only showed some increase of connective tissue. The remaining 21 showed more or less the changes described under Group 2 a and c. If the animals in this Group 5 are divided according to the infection being acute (11 animals) or tuberculous (12 animals), we arrive at the following figures for the percentage of the gravest changes.

Table 4.

	Animals with	
	acute infect.	tuberculous infect.
Hemorrhages per cent.	0	33
Necroses » »	46	67
Calcium grains » »	27	67
Giant-nuclei cells » »	36	67
Increased connective tissue . » »	73	92

Group 6. 3 animals with healing scurvy, No. 76, 77, 78. (Figs. 63, 64.)

These animals got a non-protective dose of orange juice, and one animal in the series, No. 75, died and showed all the grave muscular changes described above. In so far as they might have been present also in No. 76—78, these changes have nearly disappeared after a month's growing with a life-preserving dose of antiscorbutic. A certain hyperemia is left. There is an increase of connective tissue, and this tissue is rather fibrous. In Case 77, remaining necrotic muscle fragments are still to be seen. There are no giant-nuclei cells, but muscle cells lie heaped close together in a manner not seen in normal cases. Cases 76 and 77 have in some spots single giant cells of the type seen in regeneration: a large cell, rich in protoplasm, with a big syncytial light nucleus.

Group 8. 17 animals without scurvy and with an infection, which in 15 animals is tuberculous.

No. 13, 14, 15, 17, 19, 97, 104, 105, 108, 109, 110, 111, 167, 174, 176, 181, 182.

No. 97 and, with a certain local exception, No. 176 show no muscular changes, whereas the others show certain of the changes described under Group 2 c, *i. e.*, a swelling and homogenization of a part of the muscle fibres. There is no hyperemia, no hemorrhage, no increase of connective tissue, no pronounced necrosis, no giant-nuclei cells.

Group 8. 4 animals on relative inanition, without scurvy. No. 184, 185, 186, 187.

All the 4 animals showed certain of the changes described under Group 2 a and c, that is, a certain hyperemia, homogenization and swelling of some muscle fibres, slenderness of others and formation of giant-nuclei cells. In Case 84 (8 days) and 87 (7 days) there are only few of these, together with more numerous accumulations of muscle cells, the nuclei of which through a general diffuse dark colouring resemble those

of the giant-nuclei cells. In Case 86 (11 days) the giant-nuclei cells are more numerous, in Case 87 (14 days) still more, consequently growing in number the longer the animal has starved. No hemorrhages, no necroses, no calcium grains, no certain increase of connective tissue.

In the cases of all these 8 groups fatty degeneration of the musculature can only be stated in one case. This corroborates the conception of HART and LESSING as well as of ASCHOFF and KOCH, that fatty degeneration does not belong to the scorbutic changes in the musculature.

In 7 cases of advanced scurvy the elastin of the musculature has been stained according to Weigert without any noteworthy result.

Summary and discussion.

From this investigation it is obvious that in guinea-pig scurvy there is a real myopathy with characteristic features. Further it has become clear that the hemorrhages are of no importance to the genesis of this myopathy, even though they may secondarily and locally aggravate it. The essential change of the musculature — together with general hyperemia and local hemorrhages — is an atrophy. This atrophy appears already in the latent stage, though it can not be patho-anatomically stated as early as the changes in the teeth. It is general in the sense that it is seen in the most different muscles, though it is not uniformly extended within them, but, like the bone changes, it seems to have a predilection for certain places near the connections with tendons and periosteum (the supposed growth zone of the muscles). This scorbutic atrophy is soon combined with pronounced necroses which show a great tendency towards calcification. We also meet with a kind of giant-nuclei cells of which up till now no detailed description has been given. These giant-nuclei cells will have been observed by Hayem, by HOLST and FRÖLICH (»small accumulations of the multiplied sarcolemma

cells») and by ASCHOFF and KOCH («wuchernde Kernen»). These investigators interpret them as being an attempt at regeneration. Large, multi-nucleated cells should, according to HERXHEIMER, be thus regarded in every case, when they appear in atrophic processes. These giant-cells are described by Herxheimer as having abundant protoplasm. Giant-cells of this type I have also observed in the healing cases 76 and 77, and I think Herxheimer's interpretation applicable to them. The giant-nuclei cells observed by me in scurvy and in inanition, call for some special remarks. These cells appear in the larger number, the longer the scurvy or inanition has lasted. They have very sparse endoplasm, in most cases there is none to be seen at all. The nucleus, which has a homogeneous colour and sometimes looks like a big irregular lump, sometimes like a syncytium of smaller, in different ways coherent nuclei. It may have the width of an ordinary muscle fibre and the length be several times the width. These giant-nuclei cells are seen in the same places, where the other muscular changes in scurvy are localized. They are often seen in the muscle fibre surrounded by a lighter zone. The descriptions above, in cases of inanition and in healing scurvy, where accumulations of muscle-cell nuclei lie close together, suggest that the giant-nuclei cells arise through the cleaving of the muscle nuclei not being completed. The rapid disappearance of these cells when the scurvy is healing is then explained through the cleaving of the cell syncytium, when the different cells at first remain lying very close together.

In these giant-nuclei cells the relation of the nucleus to the plasm, »a biologically very important expression of the vital conditions and the activity of the special cell form» (E. Holmgren), is further altered to the favour of the nucleus. This alteration is seen after insufficiency of the food in necessary nutriments (lack of antiscorbutic, general inanition), which if it goes on further, may cause necrosis. The appearance of these cells may signify, that the regeneration that is normally going on in the muscles is not altogether stopped though it does not lead to a sufficient final result.

The appearance of giant-nuclei cells in scurvy might be interpreted not as a sign characteristic of this disease, but as a sign of terminal inanition. This is gainsaid by Case 156, where during the last month there was no decrease, but on the contrary an increase in weight. About this, see further p. 131.

As to the action of an existing tuberculosis on the scorbutic muscular changes, see p. 164.

Conclusions.

1. In guinea-pig scurvy symptoms can be clinically observed, denoting that the muscles are early overtaken by the disease. This is the first clinical sign of scurvy.

2. Patho-anatomically, in guinea-pig scurvy a myopathy is demonstrable, the nature of which is an atrophy combined with necrosis.

3. The characteristics of this scorbutic atrophy is a general hyperemia, the appearance of certain giant-nuclei cells, a great tendency towards necrosis and the impregnation of the necroses with calcium, and hemorrhages in the places exposed to mechanical strain or traumata.

4. This scorbutic myopathy can patho-anatomically be demonstrated already in the latent stage, somewhat later than the changes in the teeth.

Muscles of the alimentary canal. (Tongue.)

Of these muscles I have only subjected the tongue to study. HART and LESSING have described calcium deposits in necrotic muscular fibres in the tongue of one of their scorbutic monkeys. The musculature of the tongue has been examined by me in the sections through the lower jaw, of which there is a summary p. 41. In these sections I have as a rule only found slight changes in the muscles of the tongue, and even those not very extensive. No giant-nuclei cells, no calcified necrosis. Only once a hemorrhage. It may be that a more thorough study of series of sections, in which WESTIN is now engaged, will alter this result.

Other muscles (heart). (Fig. 66—70.)

It is proved that the heart shows the same changes as the skeleton musculature.

Of other muscles I have only subjected the heart to a closer examination.

LEVEN was of opinion (1871) that in human scurvy fatty degeneration of the heart muscle is constant, and wished to explain the changes in the other organs, as also the final issue, as conditioned by this. HAYEM found (1871) astrophy, fatty degeneration and pigment, KOCH (1889) »neben hämorrhagischer Pericardit *Atrophie der Muskulatur*¹ und fettige Degeneration, sonst Blutungen unter den Pericard». In 1905 SATO and NAMBU also found *hyperemia and atrophy with increase of connective tissue*¹ between the muscle fibres. ASCHOFF and KOCH write in 1918: »Neben wohlerhaltene Muskulatur, die allenthalb stärkere Anaemie aufweist, sieht man andere Fälle, wo *eine allgemeine Atrophie der Muskelfasern, Pigmentablagerungen*¹, und wieder andere Fälle, wo eine deutliche, aber im Ganzen nur geringe Verdichtung des Bindegewebes zu konstatieren ist». They arrive, however, to the same conception as regarding the skeleton musculature, that »*das mikroskopische Bild der Herzmuskulatur abhängig zu sein scheint von dem allgemeinen körperlichen Zustande und von den begleitenden Krankheiten*».¹ As to the heart muscle of scorbutic monkeys, it is to be noted that HART and LESSING (1913) found calcium deposits also here. HART has in 1909 described the conditions of the calcification of the heart muscle, and I agree with his opinion. The literature is summarized by HESS (1921) in his monography thus: »Although hypertrophy and dilatation of the heart have been noted by several observers² microscopic changes have rarely been recorded. Meyer, and also Leven, report fatty degeneration of the muscle fibres, which, however,

¹ The italics are mine.

² I have also, in manifest scurvy in guinea-pigs, seen dilatation of the heart auricles to be constant. The examination of the ventricle walls has not been carried out with sufficient regularity to allow a conclusion.

was found by Aschoff and Koch in only one case. Sato and Nambu described an increase of connective tissue, and others anemia and pigmentation. Thickening of the pericardium and subserous hemorrhages also occur.» FINDLAY (1921) found in scorbutic guinea-pigs loss of striation of the muscle fibres, capillary congestion and an edema of the interstitial connective tissue, but did not find any collections of granules such as those described by Hart and Lessing.

I have examined the heart musculature from 19 guinea-pigs, of which 13 had scurvy in different stages. They may be grouped thus:

1 healthy animal, No. 171.

1 animal with scorbut manifestus gravior without infection, No. 113.

4 animals with scorbut mitior latens levior without infection, No. 144, 160, 161, 162, m. pr. d. 0.5—0.8, 92 days.

2 animals with scorbut manifestus mitior and an infection, No. 132, 133, m. pr. d. 0.2, 43—86 days; both with tuberculosis.

6 animals with scorbut latens and an infection; 4 had scorbut latens mitior extensus, m. pr. d. 0.3, 40—77 days, No. 136, 138, 139, 142; two had scorbut latens mitior levior, m. pr. d. 0.5—0.8, 18—44 days, No. 145 and 164. All without No. 145 had tuberculosis.

1 animal without scurvy, with a tuberculous infection, No. 109.

4 animals on relative inanition, without scurvy, No. 184—187.

The sections have been stained, some with hematoxylin-eosin, some with cresylic violet according to Weigert or Schulz.

The healthy animal and three of the four animals with scorbut levior without infection show normal pictures of heart musculature, Fig. 66. The other 10 scorbutic animals show all, whether the disease be manifest or latent, combined with infection or not, changes in the heart musculature, which on the main are congruous and accordant with those already described with

regard to the skeleton musculature. Thus, they all have a hyperemia, without hemorrhages, and a pronounced general slenderness of the muscular fibres. In some portions the fibres are instead seen to be thickened and are at the same time homogenized, staining deeper red by eosin, Fig. 67. Except in Cases 142 and 144, the separating of the fibres into fibrils is more conspicuous than under normal conditions.

Cases 132, 133, 142 and 145, all combined with infection, show necroses of muscle fibres or bundles, and in Cases 132 and 145 these necroses are to a large extent impregnated with calcium, Fig. 68. This is sometimes arranged so as to set off the cross-striation (Fig. 69, 70). The cross-striation disappears at the homogenization, but is otherwise seen to remain long, even in the slenderest rests of fibre. The muscle cells show in every case more distinctly than under normal circumstances. They are often coarser than in healthy condition and irregular in shape, so that it seems doubtful whether they are to be called slim giant-nuclei cell or bulky muscle cells. Increase of the connective tissue is only seen in Cases 136 and 145. In the seven cases where the elastic substance round the passage of the large blood vessels from the base of the heart has been examined (No. 132, 133, 136, 138, 142, 145, 164), it appears very weak, compared to the normal. In Case 164 this atrophy can not be stated.

Case 109, on complete dietary, with tuberculosis, presents a certain slenderness of the muscle fibres, but otherwise no changes.

Among the animals on inanition, Cases 184 and 187 show normal pictures, with the exception of the elastic membranes in Case 187, as in Cases 185 and 186, appearing weaker than normally. In Case 185 typical giant-nuclei cells are visible, in Case 186 hyperemia and slenderness of muscle fibres.

Conclusion.

From this examination it is evident: 1) that the heart also is affected by the myopathy before described, the nature of which is an atrophy combined with necrosis, which

necrosis has a tendency to calcification; 2) that these changes, even necrotizing and calcification of muscle fibres, can set in already in the latent stage of scurvy.

Hereby the patho-anatomical base is given for the clinical observations of heart weakness as an early symptom of scurvy.

CHAPTER III.

Liver. (Fig. 71—78.)

The varying statements of earlier investigators about the condition of the liver in scurvy are recapitulated. As result of the author's own investigations it is established that the liver in scurvy shows constant atrophic changes.

The first author whom I have found giving an opinion about the condition of the liver in scurvy is CARL VON LINNÉ, in 1742. His utterance, though not quite clear, is yet of great interest. It is cited on page 138. In human scurvy the pathologists in the latter half of the 19th century have found very different pictures in the liver. There has been hyperemia (LUKIN, KOCH), anemia (HAYEM), hemorrhages (VARIOT, KOCH), clear atrophy in isolated cases (LUKIN), profusion of fat (LEVEN, WAGNER, HAYEM, KOCH), and so on. SATO and NAMBU in 1905 report fatty infiltration and hemorrhages as well as pigment deposits along the stroma, and URIZIO (1917) a slight interacinous increase of nuclei along the bile-ducts. ASCHOFF and KOCH publish in 1919 a particularly careful study of livers from 23 soldiers who had died with scurvy. They sum up their findings thus: »Die Leberveränderungen in Gestalt von Atrophie, fettige Degeneration und von zelliger Wucherung im Bereiche atrophischer, fast an acute Atrophie erinnernder Läppchenveränderungen, ferner der gleichzeitige Befund von frischer Cirrhose der Leber bei Scorbut sind zu verschiedenartig und andererseits zum Theil ein zu häufiger Befund bei anderen Krankheiten, als dass sie mit dem Scorbut in direkten Zusam-

*menhang zu bringen wären*¹; doch empfiehlt sich eine weitere Beobachtung des Verhaltens der Leber auf alle Fälle». HESS summarizes in 1920 the results of previous investigators. After having mentioned, how in different cases there are records of congestion, atrophy, hemorrhages, cloudy and fatty degeneration, early cirrhosis, depositions of blood pigment, he also words the conclusion thus: »In the liver no change is found with sufficient regularity to warrant its acceptance as a distinct lesion of scurvy».

HART and LESSING found in one of their monkeys »im periportalem Bindegewebe und zwar im Lumen kleiner Gefässe zu grösseren Gebilden zusammengeflossene Kalkschollen. Die Kalkablagerungen schienen in thrombotisches Material erfolgt zu sein.»

In scorbutic guinea-pigs the liver is unanimously stated to be macroscopically normal. Several authors have missed changes even in the microscopic examination (BAUMANN and HOWARD). ABDERHALDEN and WERTHEIMER declare in 1921 that they have several times observed necroses in the liver of scorbutic guinea-pigs. Their animals, however, lacked beside antiscorbutic also various other substances in their dietary. IWABUCHI (1922) found the liver columns more slender than normally.

Finally a very interesting work by HAUSMANN 1922 is to be mentioned. He studied the presence of urobilin in the urine of man in different stages of scurvy. He arrives at the conclusion that the urobilinuria does not seem to be directly connected with the hemorrhages but ought to be explained by the supposition of parenchymatous changes of the liver or spleen. Coincident with the urobilin there is an appearance and — in recovery — disappearance of achlorhydria in the gastric secretion, for which reason Hausmann presumes coincident parenchymatous changes in ventricle and liver.

The cautious manner, in which for instance Aschoff and Koch express themselves when judging about the scorbutic

¹ The italics are mine.

changes in the liver, is explained chiefly by the fact that very nearly all their cases have suffered from other diseases, generally tuberculosis, which as a rule cause changes to occur in the liver. This is yet another reason for trying to solve the question experimentally.

The liver in most of my animals has been carefully examined microscopically. The results have been brought together in groups.

As controls I have used the healthy animals enumerated under Group 6 p. 38. The study of the liver pictures of these animals once more proves the well-known facts that the liver cells in normal cases stain rather whimsically; that fat is found normally, as a rule sparse but sometimes (Case 10, after gestation!) abundant, and also pigment; that in the middle of an otherwise normal tissue and in an otherwise seemingly quite normal, healthy animal a small necrosis may incidentally be found in the liver, with (Case 11) or without (Case 95) connective-tissue reaction.

Then I collocated the changes found in 47 animals with manifest scurvy, in which there was no reason for supposing a complicating infection. No culture of bacteria has been made in these cases. In 12 cases, those first autopsied, the spleen has not been microscopically examined (No. 1, 3, 20, 26, 28, 43, 56, 67, 71, 83, 85, 86). The numbers of the remaining 35 are found in Group 3, p. 92. Of these 47 animals, 36 had had no antiscorbutic, whereas 11 had received a small dosage (0.1—0.2 m. pr. d.).

I began my investigations by examining the right lobe, the middle regions, and the left lobe of the liver separately, in sections stained by hematoxylin-eosin and frozen sections, stained by sudan. Of 8 cases thus examined, 5 showed identical changes in the different lobes, quantitatively as well as qualitatively. In the others the differences were inconsiderable; now the right, now the left lobe showing a somewhat greater change. In the continued investigation, therefore, sections from different parts of the liver were examined without it being established from which part they originated.

The microscopic pictures show in every case changes, that more or less markedly diverge from those of the controls. Parts of these changes are seen from the figures 72—78. As an example of the parenchymatous changes I quote the description of Case 1 (scorbut manifestus gravior, 24 days). »The acini appear atrophic. Venae central. lie much closer to each other than normally. Liver columns slender. Cells reduced in volume. Protoplasm generally faintly coloured; seems to be homogenized, with indistinct cell boundaries. In places where the staining of the protoplasm is specially defective, it shows a bright structure. The nucleus smaller than normally, appears atrophic; the chromatin, massed together in lumps, often gives a diffuse blue colouring to the whole nucleus. A number of parenchymatous cells have a more normal appearance. Pigment, resembling bilious pigment, sparse in the parenchymatous cells. Fat sparse, diffuse. The cells of the stroma are more than normally prominent. This seems due partly to the diminishing of the parenchymatous cells, partly to the increase of the stroma cells.»

The change found in all of 47 scorbutic livers is an atrophy, which is most evident in the study of the nuclei. These show in all cases an extensive karyorhexis and pyknosis. The protoplasm also is changed in the manner described for Case 1, the cells are small, the columns slender.

Fat is seen in most cases. Only in 6 cases it is absent. In 3 cases the fat is concentrated centrally in the acini, in 3 cases peripherally, but in most cases distributed diffusely. In many cases there are only isolated fat drops. In 20 cases the adiposis is more considerable.

The *connective tissue* of the stroma seems slightly increased in 17 cases. In 16 other cases the cells of the connective tissue are also prominent compared to the parenchymatous cells, but one has the impression that this is caused by the atrophy of the latter. Finally, an increase of the interlobular connective tissue can in 12 cases with certainty be excluded.

A brownish yellow (bilious) *pigment* is seen in most cases (38). Only in 7 it is abundant.

Necroses are found in half the number of cases (22). They are sometimes small but often much extended and may even spread through large portions of the liver. Only in 3 cases (No. 85—87, 39—43 days, 0.1 m. pr. d.) the necroses are surrounded by connective-tissue cells. In 12 cases (26 %), the strata, depicted in Fig. 76, 77, 78 of blue-grey to blue-black grains or lumps are seen, which by treatment with sulphuric acid are proved to contain calcium. These cases are No. 7, 24, 71, 72, 73, 74, without antiscorbutic, 25—29 days, and No. 67, 70, 84, 85, 86, 122, with a m. pr. d. of 0.1—0.2, 39—55 days. Thus in cases of scorbüt manifestus gravior (0 antiscorbutic), calcium has been found in the liver necroses in 6 of 36 cases, that is, 16 %, whereas among 11 cases of scorbüt manifestus mitior (0.1—0.2 m. pr. d.) it was found in 5 cases (46 %). In explaining this difference we have first of all to observe the longer lifetime of the latter animals. The calcium is in the smaller necroses often distributed diffusely throughout the necrosis, in the larger ones stratified in a border zone. Fat is often seen all over the necrosis like hardly visible drops. Besides it appears in many cases as a zone of large fat drops outside, inside or together with the calcium zone, or as a solitary border zone, Fig. 75. In some cases there is also a border zone of brown pigment (not iron) round the necrosis. Thus we see necroses of different appearance, from small ones without reaction up to the very large, while in or around them brown pigment, calcium, fat and connective tissue appear in different combinations. These large necroses have an irregular form and have no regard to the acinus-delineation. A connection between their boundary-lines and any definite liver structure is not demonstrable.

To summarize, we have thus found in these 47 scorbutic livers the picture of a simple atrophy. In some cases (No. 3, 6, 7, 58, 59) this atrophy has been so slight and uncomplicated that its significance may be disputed. In most cases it is more pronounced, combined with degenerative changes (fat), combined with necrosis, which may be very extensive. Thus, there are very

considerable changes to be seen diffusely in Cases 20, 21, 23, 41, 45, 53, 73, 74, 84, 85, 86. *An outstanding feature in these necroses is that they often show calcifications.*

As a third group 15 cases of scurvy were examined, which were complicated by an infection. The animals had the numbers 5, 27, 29, 31, 46, 48, 49, 50, 55, 57, all with scorbut gravior, 12—35 days; and No. 60, 63, 64, 66 and 87, with scorbut mitior, 0.1—0.2 m. pr. d., 4—39 days. It may be said briefly that all these cases show liver changes like those just described. Necroses and considerable fat deposition are present in about the same proportion in the animals with an infection, as in those without one (respectively, ca. 50 per cent. for necroses, ca. 40 per cent. for stronger fatty degeneration). This conformity must, however, be looked upon as an accidental result, as in the infected animals different factors act in opposite direction, namely the shortened lifetime and the complicating infection. If we compare animals in the two groups which are comparable with regard to the nature of the scurvy and the lifetime, we find the changes of protoplasm and nuclei more pronounced in animals with a complicating infection. The increase of the connective tissue, however, is seen among these in a smaller number of cases, 20 % against 39 %, which seems plausible. The infection was in 7 cases an infection of the upper air passages, in 2 cases pneumonia, in 1 case septicemia, in 1 case enteritis, and in 4 cases of uncertain localization. The most marked changes in the liver were found in the case with enteritis (Case 31). Even if we are justified in ascribing to the infection a great importance for the liver picture, in this case as well as in those that died early, it is as a rule impossible to decide in which degree the scurvy and in which the infection may have brought about the changes in the liver.

As another group I have placed the animals which had a carefully measured antiscorbutic dosage, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.8 and > 1 of the minimum protective dose. Only the ani-

mals from No. 79—178, that were not infected with tuberculosis, are here dealt with. (For the liver changes in tuberculosis, see Part IV.)

0.1 m. pr. d. Animals 120—123, 15—42 days.

Considerable changes with necroses in all cases, in the first three cases calcifications in the necroses. Very strong fatty degeneration in the first, slight in the other cases. No increase of connective tissue.

0.2 m. pr. d. Animals 128—131, 15—29 days.

In all cases strong atrophy with extended necroses, more (No. 128—130) or less (131) fat, and a trace of regeneration from the bileducts. Inconsiderable connective-tissue reaction. In Case 131 calcium deposits.

0.3 m. pr. d. Animals 135—138, 37—83 days.

In all cases atrophy with fat, and a certain regeneration with a number of round cells. In Case 138 necroses.

0.5 m. pr. d. Animals 144—146.

Heterogeneous pictures. In Case 144, killed after 92 days, only fat, otherwise normal picture. Case 145 (infection, 18 days), atrophy, calcified necroses, plenty of fat. Case 146, killed after 92 days, atrophy, not much fat.

0.7 m. pr. d. Animals 151—153.

Cases 151 and 153 (92 and 90 days), a certain peripheral hyperemia in the acini, slight general atrophy, fat.

Case 152 (infection, 22 days), foci of granulation tissue, necroses with connective tissue; the rest like the preceding cases.

0.8 m. pr. d. Animals 159—162.

No marked atrophy, not much fat, a certain hyperemia. In Case 159 a large necrosis.

> 1 m. p. d. Animals 167—170, 175—178.

Case 167 (appendicitis, 8 days), not much fat, a few small necroses with connective-tissue reaction.

- 168, 169, 170 (killed while healthy), normal picture.
 175 (infection, 17 days) some fat peripherally.
 176 (peritonitis, pneumonia), hyperemia, diffuse general fatty degeneration, strong protoplasm changes (pyknosis).
 177 (broncho-pneumonia, 28 days) hyperemia, some fat.

Thus we find that the manifest forms of scorbuit mitior (0.1—0.3 m. pr. d.) show strong liver changes like those already described above. The latent forms, on the other hand (0.5—0.8 m. pr. d.), have less prominent or even (0.8 m. pr. d.) quite slight changes, except in complicating infections, but in such cases we are met by the insurmountable difficulty of establishing the *degree* of the etiological significance of scurvy. Yet we may be justified in drawing the inference that in these latent cases with extensive changes (*e. g.*, Case 145) the infection and the scurvy have co-operated, or in other words, that *the liver of an animal that for some time back has been without a sufficient antiscorbutic dose in its dietary and therefore is suffering from a scorbuit latens mitior, is more readily injured by an infection than a normal liver, so that degeneration and necrosis set in.*

In mentioning certain cases of liver atrophy in human scurvy quoted in the literature, HESS writes that these may be explained as a consequence of the cardiac changes in scurvy. For some of my cases such an explanation might not be excluded, the atrophy in 5 of the cases (No. 43, 44, 77, 78, 88) appearing specially pronounced round the venae centrales. However, the stasis can not explain the extensive changes. *The most plausible explanation is that the hepatic cells are in need of antiscorbutic for their activity and growth, and that when this substance is lacking or deficient in the food, an atrophy of the liver parenchyma takes place.*

With regard to the constant, fairly early and very extensive atrophy in scurvy, I may mention McCarrison's hypothesis, that in beriberi B-vitamin is taken from the cells of the liver to other, rapidly growing organs. The liver in rats, pigs and cattle is found to be rich in C-vitamin (PARSONS).

Nothing, however, in these experiments seems directly to verify this hypothesis as applicable in scurvy.

The four animals on relative inanition (No. 184—187) show generally normal liver pictures, and this though they have decreased in weight more than the scorbutic animals, absolutely as well as relatively to the body-weight. In Case 185, however, a number of pyknotic nuclei are seen; in Case 186 there is in the edge of the liver a fairly large necrosis and close to this a couple of smaller ones, in which small blue-grey grains (calcium) are enclosed.

For some of the animals I have calculated the weight of the liver in relation to the body-weight. This seems to me to be of greater interest than the absolute figures. The result is seen from the table below, where the first figure in each row indicates the weight percentage and the second the number of animals for which the figure is calculated.

Table 5.

Liver weight per cent. of body weight		
	No tuberc. inf.	Tuberc. inf.
Complete dietary	5.8 (9)	7.4 (8)
Basal scurvy diet	4.9 (3)	6.4 (3)
Basal sc. d. + 0.1 m. pr. d.	6.0 (3)	7.0 (3)
» » » + 0.2 » » »	6.7 (3)	9.5 (2)
» » » + 0.3 » » »	9.3 (3)	8.2 (2)
» » » + 0.5 » » »	6.0 (4)	7.7 (4)
» » » + 0.7 » » »	5.8 (2)	7.6 (4)
» » » + 0.8 » » »	6.1 (4)	12.8 (2)
» » » + >1 » » »	5.8 (8)	7.0 (5)
Relative inanition	4.1 (2)	

The conclusion to be drawn from these figures, founded on a small number of cases, is that the liver in scurvy on the whole keeps the weight relation to the body which it has

in normal cases. In tuberculosis the liver weight is relatively increased, as well in animals on complete diet as in those on scurvy diet.

CHAPTER IV.

Spleen. (Fig. 79—85.)

It is shown that besides the hemosiderosis, and sometimes hemorrhage, described by previous authors, the spleen in scurvy is the site of an atrophy of the lymphoid tissue.

Of the few and varying observations of earlier authors about the condition of the spleen in human scurvy, HESS in 1920 makes the following summary: »The spleen shares the general congestion of the internal organs. Sato and Nambu invariably found large numbers of pigment granules in this organ. Hirschsprung noted many Malpighian corpuscles, Reinert describes a true hyperplasia of the splenic pulp and others mention infarcts and subcapsular hemorrhages.» To this summary may only be added, that LUKIN among his cases describes one with simple atrophy of the spleen, and also the following quotation from ASCHOFF and KOCH 1919: »Die Veränderungen, die die Milz aufweist, sind mannigfacher Natur, aber wohl in der Hauptsache durch sekundäre Erkrankungen bedingt. Die mit dem Scorbut in Zusammenhang zu bringenden Veränderungen entsprechen hauptsächlich denen, die auch an den Lymphdrüsen zu sehen sind. Vor allem findet sich Pigmentablagerung, besonders in den Retikulumzellen um die Trabekeln. Aber auch in den Pulpazellen wird Pigment gefunden. Weiter zeigt die Milz öfters die Zeichen von Stauung, auch kleine Blutungen werden beobachtet. *In anderen Fällen findet sich Vermehrung und Umwandlung der Pulpazellen in dichtgedrängte, mehr spindelige Zellform unter Zurücktreten des lymphatischen Gewebes.*»¹ About this observation, which in the light of the present experiments becomes of great interest, ASCHOFF and KOCH say nothing in their discussions of the scorbutic changes.

¹ The italics are mine.

It must be noted that CRAMER and MOTTRAM as scorbutic changes briefly mention great atrophy of the lymphoid tissue, the thymus, the spleen and the lymphatic glands.

I have found nothing in the literature about the scorbutic changes of the guinea-pig spleen. HESS says quite shortly: »The spleen is generally normal».

The complicating effect of an infection on human material, which, as ASCHOFF and KOCH point out, nearly always asserts itself, makes the advisability of solving the problem by experimental investigation quite especially obvious with regard to the spleen.

Apart from the tuberculous animals, the spleen has been examined more closely in 88 of my guinea-pigs, 62 of which with scurvy. What Hess says about the macroscopic appearance of the spleen in scurvy holds true. It is generally normal. I therefore dwell upon the microscopic picture and for that study divide my material in different groups.

Group 1: 14 healthy animals without scurvy or infection. No. 9, 11, 12, 98, 100, 101, 102, 103, 168, 169, 178, 183.

The picture of the spleen is in all these cases normal. See Fig. 79, 83.

Group 2: 5 animals without scurvy, with an infection. No. 107, 167, 175, 176, 177.

The infection was in Case 167 a colitis, in the last three a pneumonia, which in Case 176 was combined with peritonitis. All these cases, with the exception of No. 167, show the typical picture of an infected spleen with hyperemia, hyperplasia of the pulp, catarrh of the sinus. In Case 167, on the other hand, the spleen, besides sparse lymphoid elements, shows a general hyalinization of the stroma and numerous necroses, a picture indicating a very powerful toxic effect.

Group 3: 35 animals with scorbut manifestus without infection. 11 have a scorbut mitior with a minimum protective dose of 0.1—0.3 (No. 58, 59, 68, 69, 70, 75, 84, 88, 89, 122,

123), whereas 24 have a scorbuit gravior (0 antiscorbutic), (No. 6, 7, 8, 21, 23, 24, 25, 35, 37, 39, 40, 41, 42, 44, 45, 51, 52, 53, 72, 73, 74, 112, 113, 115).

The spleens of all these animals show changes which are illustrated by Fig. 80, 81, 83. Under the loupe the spleen shows a less homogeneous appearance than ordinarily; the structure seems coarse-meshed. The meshes are remaining strands of lymphoid tissue, between which the other parts of the pulp, where lymphocytic elements are nearly lacking, appear light in colour. With higher magnifying power the open capillaries in the lymph follicles stand out strikingly as bright gaps. Hyperemia in the whole spleen is constant. In the follicles it is not the lymphocytes or lymphoblasts that dominate in an advanced stage, but large starshaped bright cells with a large bright nucleus, reticulum-cells. This change begins in the periphery of the »germ-centre». These large reticulum-cells are also more than normally prominent in the rest of the pulp. The pulpa cells nearly all have an abundance of ferruginous pigment. Such pigment is also often seen in the bright smaller cells which, in the absence of the lymphocytes, fill the efferent sinuses. In some cases (No. 8, 35, 37) where the lymphocytic elements are more prominent, they have more the character of lymphoblasts than of lymphocytes. Sometimes (23, 24, 25, 26) there are numerous hemorrhages in the spleen. It seems that the hemosiderin contents in the spleen ought to be connected with the hemorrhages in the body, as it is specially abundant (Case 21, 43) or more sparse (26, 42, 70, 72), according to the hemorrhages in others organs being more or less strong and numerous.

Group 4: 10 animals with manifest scurvy and an acute infection. 5 animals have a scorbuit manifestus gravior (0 antiscorbutic), No. 5, 27, 49, 50, 55, while 5 have a scorbuit mitior (0.1—0.2 m. pr. d.). No. 60, 66, 87, 90, 121.

In 5 cases the reaction of the spleen is distinct with hyperplasia of the pulp and increase of the lymphocytic elements. With this picture, however, features from that described

for the preceding group are mingled. In two cases (49, 87) the lymphocytic reaction is weak or uncertain, and in three other cases (50, 60, 66) it is totally absent. In some cases (49, 66) the splenic changes described above as being typical of scurvy are not apparent; in the others (50, 60, 63, 87) they are distinct.

Group 5: 6 animals with scorbüt latens levior (m. pr. d. 0.5—0.8), all 92 days, No. 144, 146, 151, 160, 161, 162. No infection.

These animals all show a splenic picture which, with regard to the decrease or almost absence of the lymphocytes in the germ-centre and the appearance of large bright reticulum-cells, agrees with that of Group 3. Yet in the follicles mitoses of lymphoid cells and lymphoid elements in the efferent sinuses are seen, even if they are larger than under normal circumstances and have a brighter nucleus.

Group 6: 11 animals with latent scurvy and an infection. 2 (No. 29 and 38) have a scorbüt latens gravior (0 antiscorbütic), 8—12 days. 7 (No. 63, 120, 128, 129, 130, 136, 138) have a scorbüt latens extensus, m. pr. d. 0.1—0.3, 15—64 days. 2 (No. 153, 159) have a scorbüt latens levior, m. pr. d. 0.7—0.8, 29—90 days.

A hyperplasia with lymphocytic reaction, even though sometimes weak, is seen in most cases. In Cases 38, 63, 128, 130, 136, 138 it is doubtful. As to the changes described as scorbütic, they are missing in Case 38, but are marked in Case 29, as in the seven cases of scorbüt latens extensus. In six of these seven cases there are numerous larger or smaller necroses in the spleen (Fig. 84, 85). In cases 120 and 130 these are occupied by blue-grey plates. (Fig. 84.)

The two cases of scorbüt latens levior do not show any changes of this kind. The spleen pictures here are not to be distinguished from those in Group 2.

Group 7: 3 animals with healing scurvy. No. 76, 77, 78. Under a low power the changes are seen to resemble those

in scurvy, but with a higher power a large number of small dark lymphocytes appear between the numerous large bright reticulum-cells. These quite normal-looking lymphocytes also fill the efferent sinuses in long rows. In the germ-centres there are numerous mitoses of lymphoid cells to be seen.

Group 8: 4 animals on relative inanition. No. 184—187.

Among these, the spleen picture in Case 187 (lymphadenit. submax. supp., 7 days) can not be distinguished from that of a typical splenic tumour. In Case 185 (14 days) the spleen is very nearly similar to that of a healthy animal. In Cases 184 (8 days) and 186 (11 days) there is on the other hand a general paucity of lymphocytic elements, even if there are lymphocytes seen in the efferent sinuses.

Summary. According to this examination of the spleen from 88 guinea-pigs, of which 62 with scurvy, this organ is, in cases of scurvy, the site of changes which may be summed up as *an atrophy of the lymphoid tissue*. To this has to be added *hemosiderosis*, and sometimes *hemorrhages*. The scorbutic spleen often shows a weak or *no lymphocytic reaction to infections*. With these *necroses* easily set in.

This splenic change can be traced already at an early period in the latent forms of scurvy. In this it is analogous to the changes in the marrow of the long bones. The analogy also manifests itself in the disappearance of the specific elements being seen preferably in the region of the most intensive cellular activity (the epiphyseal ends, the Malpighian corpuscles).

The lymphoid tissue in other places.

Different lymph-glands from a number of animals have been examined, though not from so many as with regard to the spleen. Without quoting each separate case it may briefly be stated that the changes in the lymph-glands in advanced scurvy are constant and of the same nature as is described above concerning the lymphoid tissue of the spleen. The description which SCHOEDEL gives of the frame-work marrow in

the epiphyseal ends, that it seems as if the specific elements were brushed away and only the reticulum were left, can be used as an adequate description of the changes in the lymph-glands in advanced cases.

The same changes, withdrawal of the lymphoid elements and prominence of large bright reticulum-cells, are also observable already in latent cases in the lymphoid tissue, which is found in the lungs along the bronchi and is seen like nodules at their ramifications. Lymph-nodules changed in this manner in the lungs may become the site of an abscess (Case 29), as also the lymph-glands in general, according to numerous statements in the literature, easily form abscesses, »scurbic buboes». This has also been the case with the submaxillary gland in my animals No. 5, 30, 46, 49, 60, 63, 64 and 90.

CHAPTER V.

Kidney. (Fig. 86—90.)

It is shown how in scurvy the kidney presents two different kinds of changes, a certain atrophy, as in other organs, and besides calcium deposits that may be explained in connection with a rapid calcium excretion.

About the state of the kidneys in scurvy there are but few reports in the literature. LUST and KLOCHMANN suppose that scurvy is due to a disturbance of the calcium excretion, without defining this disturbance more closely. The pathological findings are summarized by HESS (*l. c.* p. 102) thus: »The kidneys are often normal. On the other hand, various forms of nephritis are found, with cloudy swelling or interstitial change — a not infrequent complication of scurvy. More typical of the primary disease are congestion and hemorrhages». HAYEM found fatty degeneration in this organ, and ASCHOFF and KOCH a slight change of this kind in one case.

I have examined the kidneys in 20 of my cases. These are grouped as follows.

3 healthy animals, No. 168, 178, 183. (Fig. 86.)

The two first show a normal picture of the kidney. No. 183, on the other hand, that for some time had suffered from beriberi-like symptoms, completely gone more than a month before it was killed, showed numerous calcium deposits in the wall and lumen of the renal tubes; of which more on p. 99. For the rest the kidney seemed normal also in this case.

13 cases of scurvy.

2 of these cases, No. 113 and 119, were scorbut manifestus gravior (0 antiscorbutic), 19—21 days, the latter with tuberculosis, though not in the kidney, the former without infection.

3 were scorbut manifestus mitior, No. 121, 131, 133, 4 scorbut latens extensus, No. 135, 136, 139, 142, m. pr. d. 0.1—0.3, 21—86 days, all with an infection which in three cases was tuberculous, yet without tuberculosis in the kidney. 4 were scorbut latens levior; 3, No. 144, 161, 162, m. pr. d. 0.5—0.8, 92 days, without infection, 1 case, No. 152, m. pr. d. 0.7, 22 days, with an infection, abscesses in various organs but not in the kidneys.

These 13 cases of scurvy all show changes which in certain cases are accordant, in others not. A general hyperemia is found in all kidneys except in Cases 135, 136, 139. All without exception show an atrophy of the epithelium which first of all manifests itself in a large number of the glomeruli looking atrophic (Fig. 87). In Case 162 this is but little pronounced. Further there is an extensive pyknosis of the nuclei of the epithelium cells and a homogenization of the protoplasm, which, in the 6 cases with manifest scurvy and an infection, stains very deficiently. In most cases the connective tissue seems to be increased in the cortex.

Pronounced necroses are not seen in any case except in connection with calcium deposits. Such were present in all cases except in those two that had a scorbut manifestus gravior, No. 113 and 119. The pictures (Fig. 88, 89, 90) give an impression that here we have to deal with a different process from that described for the other organs where we may suppose as probable a secondary calcium deposit in a preceding atrophying or necrotic tissue. In the kidney the pictures are more

varying. The glomeruli, the epithelium of which seems to be most changed, are free from calcium. But it is present in the tubuli, from the tubuli contorti downwards to the collecting tubes. The calcium lumps are differently situated. Either they lie as more or less elongated formations between the capillaries and the epithelium, which they bulge out into the lumen. Or else the calcium deposits are seen in the epithelium cells themselves, sometimes in the basal part of the cell between the nucleus and the capillaries, sometimes filling the whole of a cross-section of a tubulus contortus or a looped tube of Henle. Finally the calcium concretion is seen lying wholly or partially in free lumen. In the study of the calcium masses within the lumina one gets the impression that more or less changed epithelium cells often form part of the masses.

These pictures seem more likely to indicate a hasty calcium excretion than necroses which are secondarily calcified. Only in one case, No. 135, I have found, besides pictures like those now described, a place where a primary necrosis seems to be in course of becoming calcified. The kidneys in scurvy would then be able to exhibit calcium foci of two principally different kinds. In discussing the above-described pictures, which look like excretion pictures, it must be noted, first that the glomeruli are quite free, and then that calcium is lacking in the two cases with scorbüt gravior, whereas it is present in all cases of scorbüt mitior, manifestus as well as latens. See further p. 128.

It has to be investigated whether these calcium concretions in scurvy can be demonstrated through Roentgen rays. They seem to be of interest for the pathogenesis of nephrolithiasis. As a circumstance producing renal calculi excessive flesh-dietary has been stated. Might possibly the injurious circumstance be lack of fresh vegetable food?

4 animals on relative inanition, No. 184—187.

These animals show a hyperemia of the kidney. Also epithelium changes are seen in all the four cases, but they are very slight. No necroses, no calcium lumps. A light increase of connective tissue seems to take place in the cortex.

By the way may be mentioned a finding in the kidney of animal No. 183. This animal, when bought, suffered from beriberi-like symptoms (constant twisting of the neck and head to one side, difficulty in keeping balance). The animal was put on complete dietary. After a month the weight curve began to rise, after another month all clinical symptoms had disappeared. When after another six weeks the animal was killed, it seemed well, and at the histological examination no changes were found in the organs, except in the kidneys. Here there was a picture of multiple calculi, lying in the free lumen of the tubuli and under the epithelium. In fact, quite the same picture as with regard to scurvy, I had felt bound to interpret as sign of a precipitate excretion of calcium salts. The calcium metabolism in beriberi does not seem to have been especially studied. In this disease, however, a general atrophy and degeneration of different organs is recorded, which may be supposed during the active stage of the disease to retain in the body considerable amounts of calcium, excreted in recovery. It may also be mentioned that PADUA 1919 (quoted after FUNK) saw a definite relationship between beriberi and renal calculi in the Philippines. OSBORNE and MENDEL found phosphatic calculi in the bladder of a great number of rats kept on a diet, poor in vitamin A. FUNK considers (1922) all these cases to be associated with the indirect influence of the vitamins, as »it is apparent that a local infection is the real cause of this calculus formation». After my findings another interpretation will be more probable. It is possible that, as I have supposed for scurvy and beriberi, a disturbance in the state of the calcium may be the reason and that we here have to deal with a symptom of calcium excretion, which may be initial (scurvy), or setting in during the period of healing (all deficiency diseases, that have given a more considerable atrophy; see further p. 139).

Summary.

In scurvy, already in the latent stage, changes seem to occur in the kidney, which may be summed up as an atrophy

often combined with necrosis and secondary calcification, as has been described with regard to liver and spleen, though the epithelium of the kidney seems to be less sensitive than the cells of those organs. Besides there are in the kidney, in latent and somewhat mitigated cases of scurvy, calcium deposits, that seemingly ought to be interpreted as a strong calcium excretion through the kidney.

CHAPTER VI.

Adrenal.

Contrary to certain earlier won results, but in accordance with others, it is stated that in the adrenal of scorbutic guinea-pigs there is an atrophy, already seen in the latent stage, but then inconsiderable.

The adrenals have by several investigators been found without remark in scurvy in man (SCHOEDEL and NAUWERK, JACOBSTHAL, INGIER, EPSTEIN, ASCHOFF and KOCH, BIERICH). Only BIERICH found in one case the medulla increased in size. In monkeys, HART and LESSING found (1913) calcium deposits in the adrenals. In guinea-pig, several investigators have found changes in the adrenals in cases of experimentally induced scurvy. RONDONI and MONTAGNANI described in 1915 such changes in guinea-pigs, fed on cereal. They found a diminution of lipoids, atrophy and degeneration of the cortex. McCARRISON describes how in guinea-pigs, fed on a diet of crushed oats and autoclaved milk, the adrenals increased in size and weight, whereas the adrenalin content absolutely decreased. On section he found »hemorrhagic infiltration, usually circumscribed in extent and situated around the periphery of the adrenal cortex», also »degenerative changes in the cellular elements of cortex and medulla», consisting of »vacuolation and disintegration of the cells with disappearance or loss of staining reactions of their nuclei». McCarrison's investigation seems to have been accepted unquestioningly, and it is everywhere quoted. It is, however, open to severe criticism. The investigation only comprised 5 guinea-pigs. These were fed on a dietary, where not only C-vitamin, but possibly also A-vita-

min was lacking or insufficient. The animals' lifetime is not reported, only that out of the 5 »several» died before showing clinical symptoms of scurvy. Consequently, for these animals there must have been a complication, probably an infection, and McCarrison's conclusion that the adrenal change present ought to be ascribed to latent scurvy, does not carry conviction. In another place (*l. c.* p. 347), McCarrison himself has laid stress upon the importance of excluding infection in judging the organic changes caused by vitamin deficiency. Leaving these animals out of consideration we find that 3 animals at the most with uncomplicated scurvy remain, and in these cases, as well as still more in Rondoni and Montagnani's investigations, the basal diet was not unquestionable.

FINDLAY (1921) could only in part corroborate McCarrison's findings. In scorbutic guinea-pigs he found »marked congestion both in the cortex and in the medulla. The cellular changes, noted by McCarrison 1919, were not well marked, except in those animals which had passed into a state of unconsciousness preceding death». Hemorrhage in the adrenal substance was only seen a few times, but extensive subcapsular hemorrhage was very common. — IWABUCHI reports in 1922 complementary examinations. After a diet of oats and dry milk he observes capillary hyperemia and degenerative changes in the cortex (chiefly zona fasciculata) and marrow: »Pyknos der Kerne, Aufhellen und Aufquellen der Protoplasma». He mentions that mitoses are not unfrequently seen in the zona fasciculata of scorbutic animals. Further he states a very marked disappearance of the lipoids in scurvy.

PEIPER, whose animals only got oats, also observed a diminution of lipoids in the cortex. His discovery is of a certain value because he observed a higher lipid content when the animals had oats and orange juice; yet it may be noted that with that juice different substances, and especially different vitamins are added to the insufficient dietary. In such examinations it must be remembered how varying and labile the lipid contents of the adrenals are even in normal cases (LANDAU).

A macroscopic change (hemorrhage) in the adrenals, I have only found once in my scorbutic guinea-pigs, above a hundred in number, though I have had an impression that the adrenals were somewhat enlarged. They have not been weighed. The adrenals of 22 animals have been microscopically examined; of these 14 had scurvy in different stages.

4 healthy animals, No. 178, 183, 188, 189, without scurvy or infection. (Fig. 92). No changes.

14 animals with scurvy.

7 of these had manifest scurvy. 4 had a scorbut manifestus gravior (0 antiscorbutic), 1 without infection (No. 113), 3 with infection (No. 116, 117, 118), all tuberculous. 3 had a scorbut manifestus mitior; 1 without infection, No. 86 0.1 m. pr. d., 43 days; 2, No. 121 and 133, 0.1—0.2 m. pr. d., 25—86 days, with an infection, in the last case tuberculous.

7 others had a latent scurvy. 3 had a scorbut latens levior m. pr. d. 0.5—0.8, 92 days, without infection. No. 144, 161, 162. 4 had a scorbut latens extensus, m. pr. d. 0.3—0.5, 59—92 days, No. 136, 139, 148, 149, with an infection, which in the three last cases was of tuberculous nature.

None of the tubercular animals had any tuberculosis in the adrenals.

These 14 scorbutic animals show on the main similar changes in the adrenals, though of different degrees (Fig. 93). In no case there is any hemorrhage. A pronounced hyperemia is found in six of the seven animals with manifest scurvy (absent in No. 113) and in three of the four animals with a latent scurvy and infection. Cellular changes, consisting in pyknosis and a defective staining of the protoplasm, are found in all the 14 cases, chiefly in the different layers of the cortex. In none of the cases with manifest scurvy it has been possible to discover a mitosis, and in the animals with latent scurvy only in Cases 161 and 162. In certain cases there is a necrosis, though only of a few cells (No. 117, 136, 149). Only in Case 133 there is a necrosis of a larger group of cells. Thus, necrosis is only found in cases where the scurvy is combined with an infection. A trace of increasing inter-

stitial connective tissue is perceived in Cases 86, 144 and 161. In Case 133 it is more distinct, and besides numerous migratory cells of different types are seen round the necroses in this case.

In some cases a yellowish brown pigment is seen in the zona reticularis. In case 86 it fills the whole of the gland. For the rest there is no pigment, except in Case 113 a focus of blue-grey lumps, which might be interpreted as calciferous. I have not found any sure calcium deposit in the adrenals.

4 animals on relative inanition, No. 184—187 (Fig. 94).

These animals show reciprocally corresponding changes. First of all there is a hyperemia. The two cases that had lived longest, No. 185 and 186, also show hemorrhages in the parenchyma, localized to the zona reticularis. Cellular changes, such as are described in the scorbutic animals, are also met with in the inanition animals, but in a much lesser degree. No necroses, no connective tissue. On the other hand the inanition animals show a lively cell division. Whereas in healthy animals this must be searched for and is totally absent in animals with pronounced scurvy (Iwabuch made an observation to the contrary), we find here, specially in the outer cortex layers, numerous pronounced mitoses (this observation was made already in 1892 by MARTINOTTI, as mentioned by IWABUCHI).

Summary and conclusions.

In scorbutic guinea-pigs changes appear in the adrenals which may be summed up as a simple atrophy, at first in connection with hyperemia. These changes begin already in the latent stage, but are then faintly pronounced, as is seen by Cases 144, 161 and 162, which were killed after having received a not completely protective dose of antiscorbutic (0.5—0.8 m. pr. d.) for three months. A tuberculous infection may in Cases 148 and 149 be supposed to have aggravated the symptoms of latent scurvy.

Thus, scorbutic animals show early changes in the adrenal, but not earlier than in other parenchymatous organs. These

changes must therefore by no means be taken as a reason for placing the adrenals in the centre of the pathogenesis of scurvy. The investigation reported in these pages, on the contrary, argues against such a conception.

CHAPTER VII.

Salivary glands.

It is confirmed, as an earlier investigator has already shown, that in scurvy there is an atrophy of the salivary glands.

The only statements about the condition of these glands in scurvy that I have found in the literature are by McCARRISON and TOVERUD. McCarrison reports that he has found the weight reduced in scurvy, compared to the normal. Toverud has in 1922 examined microscopically some of the different groups of salivary glands, though the insufficiency of the material (he does not mention the number of animals examined) deters him from pronouncing any definite statement, and he gives no details.

I have examined the sublingual gland in 39 of my cases, of which 24 had scurvy in different stages, and the submaxillary gland in 31 animals, of which 18 had scurvy. Both these glands are mixed, though the sublingual gland chiefly contains mucus-secreting cells, and the submaxillary gland chiefly serous alveoli. The examined animals are grouped thus.

No scurvy, no infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 9, 10, 11, 12.

submax. » » 168, 169, 170, 171, 188, 189.

No scurvy, with infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 15, 17, 19.

submax. » » 167, 172, 173, 175, 176, 177,
180.

Scorbut manifestus gravior, without infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 1, 4, 20, 21, 23, 25, 28.

Scorbut manifestus gravior, with infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 46, 49.

submax. » » 116.

Scorbut manifestus mitior, without infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 58, 59, 67, 75, 83, 86, 88.
 submax. » » 122, 123.

Scorbut manifestus mitior, with infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 87.
 submax. » » 125.

Scorbut latens gravior with infection:

Sublingual gland No. 29, 30.

Scorbut latens mitior extensus, with infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 18, 135, 136.
 submax. » » 129, 140, 141, 148, 149.

Scorbut latens levior, without infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 146.
 submax. » » 151, 160, 161.

Scorbut latens levior, with infection:

Sublingual gland, No. 150.
 submax. » » 147, 155, 156, 163, 164, 165.

Relative inanition:

Sublingual gland, No. 184, 185, 186, 187.

Deficiency of A-vitamin:

Sublingual gland, No. 79, 80, 81, 82.

The mucous alveoli show an essentially different picture in rest and in activity. The animals enumerated as healthy show examples of both; so do the scorbutic animals. In both stages the former differ essentially from the latter. Healthy animals show during rest wide, extended cells, the thin walls of which often bulge sideways and also penetrate unequally far towards the lumen. The nuclei lie basally and often so far from each other that they look like separate swellings of the basement-membrane. Also in rest the cells are filled with secretion, ready for discharging it outwards when needed. In scurvy another picture appears. The cells lie in the alveoli in a circle, equally narrow, equally low, with parallel, thicker walls. The nuclei, often pyknotic, lie so closely together that

a layer of cells seems to be formed inside the basement-membrane. All activity seems to be arrested. The picture of an atrophy is present. Even when the gland is seen working and the picture in consequence is changed, the difference between the scorbutic and the normal animal is evident. The change in the scorbutic gland is not nearly so great as in the healthy. Also the serous alveoli show changes in the scurvy cases, consisting in pyknosis of the nuclei and an homogenization of the cell structure. In 4 cases of scorbut latens levior, m. pr. d. 0.8, 111—92 days, No. 160, 161, 163, 164, and in Case 18, marked changes of this nature are absent. They are seen in all the other scurvy cases. In Cases 147, 148, 149, 165, rather extensive necroses are seen in the submaxillary gland, but in all these cases there is quite close to it a caseous tuberculous lymph-gland; and as there are no necroses in the salivary glands of the other cases, it is an obvious conclusion that a local influence from the tuberculosis in the lymph-gland has caused the necroses in question. No tubercle bacilli have been demonstrable in the salivary gland, nor do the histological changes in any of these cases indicate a tuberculosis in the salivary gland.

None of the 20 animals fed on complete dietary showed analogous changes, whether they were without infection or had one, acute or tuberculous. On the other hand, some slight changes of this kind were seen in two of the four cases, the dietary of which did not include cod-liver oil, No. 79 and 80, but these two had also a scorbut levior. Such slight changes were also found in one of the four animals on relative inanition, No. 184, 8 days.

Conclusions.

1. Through this investigation Toverud's supposition is corroborated, that the salivary glands in scurvy suffer an atrophy.

2. This atrophy can be demonstrated in an early stage, somewhat later than the first changes in the teeth, but earlier than the costal changes.

CHAPTER VIII.

Lung.

Previous investigators have not pointed out any constant changes in the lung caused by scurvy, nor has the present author been able to find any.

Earlier investigators have described a variety of symptoms in the lung in cases of scurvy, without any of them being stated as constant: hyperemia, hemorrhages, hyaline degeneration of the walls of the blood vessels, edema, pneumonia. No systematic examination of the lung of scorbutic guinea-pigs seems to have been undertaken. As I had not planned any such examination at the outset, no case of scorbut manifestus gravior has been examined. The 19 animals, the lungs of which have been examined, are grouped thus.

2 healthy animals, without scurvy, No. 168, 171.

4 » » » » , with infection, No. 109, 173, 177, 179.

The animals show a normal lung picture.

2 animals with scorbut manifestus mitior, 0.2 m. pr. d., 43—86 days, No. 132, 133, both with tuberculosis.

4 animals with scorbut mitior latens extensus, 0.3 m. pr. d., 40—83 days. Two with tuberculous infection. No. 139, 142; two with acute infection, No. 136 and 138.

3 animals with scorbut mitior latens levior, 0.8 m. pr. d., 92 days, No. 160, 161, 162.

Already under a low magnifying lens some of the scorbutic cases show a widening of the respiratory bronchioles and their ramifications, with thin interalveolar septa (Case 133, 139). In other cases this picture which looks rather like emphysema, is not distinctly apparent or is altogether lacking. A close study of the elastic tissue stained with cresyl-violet according to Weigert or to Schulz has not shown a congruent result. In certain cases it seems somewhat weaker than that of the normal cases, in other cases not. A study of the lymphoid tissue, which follows the ramifications of the bronchial tree, showed the atrophy described above. When a local

infection supervenes (*e. g.*, Case 139, bronchitis), the number of the lymphocytes may again increase.

However, all these changes taken together have not been sufficient for gathering a picture of the scorbutic lung, which would allow us to single out these preparations from the lung pictures of normal cases. Thus I have not found any change in the lung tissue that I can call pathognomonic. As the research has not been sufficiently comprehensive, it will be continued.

In 4 animals on relative inanition, No. 184—187, there was an atrophy of the elastic fibres of the lungs, most pronounced in the two animals that had lived longest (No. 185 and 186).

Summary:

Considering the statement of RHEINDORF in 1918, that the elastic fibres in the skin perish early in scurvy, and the observation of atrophy in the elastic membranes around the large vessels of the heart, which I have described, a similar change in the lungs might have been expected. However, it could not be stated in the animals examined.

CHAPTER IX.

Blood and blood-vessels. Hemorrhages in scurvy.

In scurvy there is, according to the results of previous investigators, a deficient regeneration of erythrocytes and polymorphous leukocytes, an initial hyperemia and a weakness of the vascular wall. This weakness is explained by the present author as a defective formation of the collagen connective tissue of the vessel and the lack of sufficient support from the atrophic tissue outside the vessel.

As a result of the investigations of later years we may set down that the cause of the hemorrhages in scurvy is a weakness in the vascular wall and not changes in the blood (HESS, BEDSON, TOBLER, UMBER *a. o.*). Yet it may be mentioned that some few authors think they have been able to state a decreased number of platelets (WASSERMANN and KIRCH) or an prolonged coagulation-time (BRANDT).

The cells of the blood, however, offer certain interesting features. The red blood-corpuscles, it is true, are sometimes in manifest scurvy normal in number (Brandt's observation of a polycythemia is isolated), the hemoglobin 100 per cent. (TOBLER), but when complications set in (hemorrhages, infections), the number of blood-corpuscles and the hemoglobin are apt to sink (many investigators, most recently SALLE and ROSENBERG) and can afterwards only with difficulty be brought to rise, till antiscorbutic is administered. But then the effect of the antiscorbutic is amazingly rapid, a matter of a few days. *The regeneration of red blood-corpuscles* thus seems to be *insufficient in scurvy*, which becomes manifest only when the demand is raised.

It is the same in the case of the white blood-corpuscles. They have often been found normal in scurvy (HERZOG, KOCH, UMBER, BEDSON a. o.). Numerous investigators (NAEGELI, LEITNER, BIERICH, SALLE and ROSENBERG, HAUSSMANN) have stated a leucopenia or in any case a failing leukocytosis in scurvy patients with infections, when a strong leukocytic reaction might have been expected. In film preparations of bone marrow, neither HART and LESSING nor FRAENKEL have been able to find abnormal cell forms. In Giemsa-stained preparations of marrow from the long bones of guinea-pigs in different stages of scurvy I have also stated that fact. Thus *in scurvy the regeneration organ of the polymorphonuclear leukocytes seems also to suffer from a weakness*, which becomes manifest when the demand is raised.

As to the conditions of the vessels, I have already remarked that when Hess establishes the failing vascularization of the frame-work marrow as the distinguishing mark between scurvy and rickets, this is true only of far advanced cases of scurvy. In initial cases there is everywhere a *hyperemia* in the growth zone of the bones as well as otherwise in the marrow and in other organs (HERZOG, FINDLAY, IWABUCHI, TOVERUD). I have met with this hyperemia in all examined organs, and I have also found it to be an early symptom.¹ The authors just mentioned unanimously state it to be a dilatation

of capillaries and veins, and this observation I have also found to agree with the conditions of my scorbutic guinea-pigs.

IWABUCHI sets forth that this dilatation of the veins can become so strong that at first sight it gives the impression of being a hemorrhage. This I have been able to verify, especially in the adrenal and the bone-marrow. When furthermore the general fragility of the organs in scurvy is considered, which easily causes artificial changes in the continuity of the vascular walls, special attention must be paid to the differential diagnosis between hyperemia and hemorrhage. The description of some earlier investigators suggest that they have not sufficiently taken this into consideration (McCARRISON, ASCHOFF and KOCH). Whether the hyperemia in scurvy is due only to the weakness of the vascular walls or of the heart, or whether an irritation from products of atrophic cells is of any account, I leave unsaid.

HART and LESSING, and INGIER describe the presence in scorbutic vessels of »hyaline thromboses», to which v. RECKLINGHAUSEN attaches great importance. In my scorbutic guinea-pigs, these »hyaline thromboses» are seen in every case. They are, however, also found in healthy animals, though to a smaller extent. Like Ingier I feel inclined to look upon them as post-mortal formations. Differences in the sinking velocity or in the sinking time of the red blood-corpuscles in scorbutic and healthy guinea-pigs may be the reason of their more frequent presence in the scurvy cases.

Hemosiderin has been found in different organs by a large number of previous investigators. The results of my investigations in this respect agree with those of Iwabuchi, that sparse hemosiderin is found locally, where there has been a hemorrhage, but for the rest in a larger quantity only in spleen and bone-marrow.

With regard to the localization of the hemorrhages, my observations completely agree with those of earlier investigators in that they are chiefly seen where an intense proliferation with congestive hyperemia takes place, as in the neigh-

bourhood of the epiphyseal lines in the long bones (JACOBS-THAL, SCHMORL, FRAENKEL, LOOSER).

Yet I am not disposed to ascribe this circumstance exclusively to the congestive hyperemia. In these growth zones a lively rebuilding takes place, also of the vessels, with strong resorption of old tissue and a vigorous new growth. When now, as in scurvy, the apposition declines until failing (see »Pathogenesis», p. 133), the effects of this ought to become manifest first of all in places where the resorption is the strongest, which is exactly in the growth zones. This explanation, which supposes the latent period of scurvy in a tissue to be the shorter, the livelier the growth is of this tissue, may also be applied to the circumstance that the latent period of absolute scurvy is the shorter, the more rapidly an individual grows; for young guinea-pigs 2 weeks, for young monkeys 2 months, for infants longer and for adults of different species a longer time than for growing individuals.

The hemorrhages, a consequence chiefly of the weakness of the vascular wall on account of deficient new growth, are thus coordinate with other symptoms in scurvy. BARLOW, KOCH and LOOSER, would assign to them a more central position as directly causing all other scorbutic changes, specially those in the bones. With regard to these the opinion of the authors in question has been proved to be erroneous by Schoedel, Schmorl, Fraenkel, Ingier, Aschoff and Koch. Concerning the musculature and the parenchymatous organs I have been able to state the same. The hemorrhages may aggravate the scorbutic atrophy locally in these organs, but as a rule they do not give rise to it.

In tuberculosis, complicating scurvy is feared, says KOCH, on account of the frequent hemorrhages in lung and intestine which then set in. In most of my guinea-pigs infected with tuberculosis that had scorbutic diet, I have found extensive hemorrhages near the primary focus in the musculature of the thigh, around tuberculous foci in spleen a. s. o.

In 1880 SWIDERSKI (quoted after Koch) indicated as cause of the hemorrhages an obstruction of the smaller vessels through

swollen endothelial cells. Swiderski notes that in scurvy the small arteries are dilated, the veins collapsed, which may agree with his hypothesis, but not with the actual facts. Koch considers Swiderski's endothelial swelling to be a post-mortal process, »jedenfalls für ebensolche Ausnahmen, nach welchen man eifrig fahndete, weil sie die Transsudation nach dem Schema der Stauungswassersucht zu erklären gestatten würden». Lately FINDLAY, without mentioning Swiderski, after an investigation on guinea-pigs repeated his statements and conclusions: »The absence of vitamin C from the diet of the guinea-pig leads to swelling and degeneration of the capillary endothelium. As a result of this swelling of the endothelium the flow of blood through the capillaries is retarded and extreme congestion occurs». — »The tissues are insufficiently oxygenated and death occurs.» In the beginning of his paper Findlay has stated, however, that the congestion does not only befall the capillaries but also the smaller venules. According to other authors and my own research, dilatation sets in even in quite large veins. How an obstruction of the capillaries is capable of dilating the veins, Findlay has omitted to explain. I have also been able to observe changes of the endothelial cells in the vessels, namely a fatty degeneration of some cells, but this change is not constant and does not occur extensively enough to be deemed essentially important. That IDE in three out of four examined Barlow cases has found changes in the medium-sized arteries, which changes he designates as endarteritis obliterans, and has not been able to find them again in guinea-pigs, may be mentioned for the sake of completeness.

In the study of my preparations I have had my attention directed to the vessels. I have often been able to confirm JACKSON and MOORE's observation that the vascular wall has seemed to be thin, both in the arteries and veins. Even in rather large vessels the cells in the vascular wall do not lie close to each other, and between them occasionally a red blood-corpuscle may be seen. In staining with cresylic violet I have not found any atrophy of the elastic tissue, such as

RHEINDORF has presumed with regard to the skin, except in the elastic membranes around the efferent vessels of the heart. But in staining on collagen according to Hansen, on the other hand, a considerable atrophy of this tissue is observed. As collagen fibrils partly constitute the walls of even very small vessels and are likely essentially to give them their firmness, this partial disappearance of the collagen fibrils must be considered an important factor in the pathogenesis of the hemorrhages. In the next part of this work will be shown that this collagen atrophy more or less overtakes all connective tissue. Besides the direct weakening of the vascular wall in the manner indicated, a certain influence ought perhaps also to be ascribed to the general atrophy with shrinking of the organ cells under the absence of normal connective-tissue reaction. Through this organ atrophy, the vessels will lack the outer support for their atrophic wall, without which the pressure from the inside must have a still greater effect.

That local irritations (SAXL and MELKA; *cf.* above, about tuberculosis) as well as static and traumatic circumstances and a physiological hyperemia can call forth hemorrhages in a vascular wall changed in this manner, seems explicable, without these circumstances therefore being counted as anything but accidental causes. Nor are we entitled to suppose with ASCHOFF and KOCH, that because the parenchymatous organs show fewer hemorrhages than the sustentacular tissues, they would be less struck by the scorbutic changes. The lesser mechanic strain on these organs is a sufficient explanation of the hemorrhages being less prominent within them.

Summary.

Previous investigators have demonstrated the presence in scurvy of 1) a deficient regeneration of red and white blood-corpuses, 2) an initial hyperemia, and 3) a weakness in the vascular walls leading to hemorrhages, chiefly localized in places where the growth is lively.

The last two of these observations have been corroborated by me. As an explanation of the latter serves the circum-

stance, pointed out by me, that the collagen connective tissue of the vessels gets atrophic in scurvy. As a possible contributory cause I have noted the lessened support from the atrophic tissues.

X.

Connective tissue.

A general atrophy in scurvy of the connective tissue, and especially of its collagen substance, is proved.

In the study of the histological pictures of different scorbutic organs it is easy to observe that the connective tissue seems atrophic. This is specially manifest with regard to formations, the thickness of which in sections from scorbutic and from healthy guinea-pigs can be directly compared, as ligamentum circumdentale (periodontium), adventitia of vessels, perineurium, membranæ propriæ of acinous glands, trabeculæ in the spleen and the collagen fibrils in the papillæ of the tongue. By staining according to Hansen, which shows the collagen sparkingly red in sections from healthy animals, it is found that just the *collagen* in scurvy is specially badly developed. This circumstance I have already mentioned concerning cartilage and bone, in which also the collagen is less developed or even lacking. A failing differentiation of the fibroblasts with inability of forming collagen fibrils is described p. 160 as characteristic of the reaction to tuberculosis of a scorbutic organism. A diminished development within the organs (lymphoid glands, liver and spleen have particularly been examined) of the collagen connective tissue I have been able to state already in cases of scorbut latens levior. This atrophy of the connective tissue will be a contributory cause of the loosening of the teeth and the appearance of hemorrhages.

As in the bone, I have also sometimes in the place of the collagen in sections, stained according to Hansen, from scorbutic parenchymatous organs, especially spleen, found yellow fibrils which possibly may be interpreted as pre-collagen. The collagen is often seen as a lump near the nucleus, while

the formation of elongated fibrils has failed. Before the formation of collagen is completely arrested, there is thus a stage when it is very unevenly distributed and irregularly arranged.

It is related by several early authors that old bone fractures at the onset of scurvy have become softened. The deficient callus-formation at fractures in scorbutically changed bones is also a common observation in the study of experimental scurvy. Also for the explanation of these circumstances, the pronounced atrophy of the collagen connective tissue in scurvy is of interest. Even if, as CARRELL has pointed out in experiments (1921), the cicatrization of wounds apparently is initiated not by an internal but by an external factor, the answer of the organism to the irritation is decided by internal factors. That a supply of full antiscorbutic dose is necessary to an answer of normal intensity, may be concluded from this investigation.

A general insufficiency in the collagen formation is not, as far as I know, earlier described.

PART III.

CHAPTER I.

Scurvy and infection.

I. Complicating acute infections in my animals.

Of my 189 animals about a third (60) have suffered from complicating acute infection. In the majority of cases it has been an acute infection of the upper respiratory canal. Pneumonia has been found in 13 animals, enterocolitis in 5, septico-pyemia in 8, peritonitis in 1, necrosis of pancreas in 1. No wide-spread epidemic has occurred. As remarkable may be mentioned the appearance of pneumonia in 4 of the 8 animals in Series 34. In Series 29 two animals showed abscesses in the spleen.

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